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BLUEPRINT

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Blueprint

Deliverable D1.3

The SUNRISE map: a public document identifying the necessary S&T resources, stateof-the-art EU facilities, available infrastructure & funding, and the criteria to make SUNRISE an open and inclusive initiative

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To tackle the science and technology (S&T) challenges posed by the climate crisis and address the need for moving towards a renewable and sustainable economy, including the energy system and the chemical industry, SUNRISE-CSA prepares a science- and technology-driven, large-scale, multidisciplinary research initiative built around a visionary unifying goal to store solar energy as fuels and chemicals while utilizing atmospheric CO₂. One of the final steps of the SUNRISE CSA is to deliver the blueprint for the large-scale research initiative and trigger calls, open for all organizations that are active in the field, for implementing the SUNRISE large-scale research initiative and contribute to its SUNERGY follow-up. In the blueprint the overall collaboration and Science & Technology framework with openness is presented, along with the identification of necessary competencies and resources including infrastructure aspects. It presents the best practice approach to address three principle research directions (PRDs) toward impact: (1) how to combine water electrolysis with CO₂ capture, (2) to determine to what extent integration of steps gives better processes in terms of efficiency, selectivity and concentration over the value chain, and (3) to find out how to obtain all the hydrogen for the transition to a low carbon, clean technology economy. The blueprint builds on the four task areas defined in the SUNRISE roadmap, *i.e.* Sustainable Hydrogen, Sustainable Ammonia, Sustainable Carbon Capture, and Sustainable Chemicals and (Jet) Fuels, which provide a strong and broad basis for future innovation and economic exploitation, as well as novel benefits for society. The single prioritizing criterion for the S&T across the three PRDs is the demonstration of the value chain from source to final product. The overarching nature of SUNRISE/SUNERGY technologies implies that this initiative can only be realised through a collaborative, long-term sustained cooperation effort. The blueprint contains a broad initial overview of organizations that we have identified that are active in these areas, including, but not restricted to, SUNRISE and Energy-X supporters, and organizations from three relevant EERA joint programs.

Integration and European added value: to address its grand S&T challenge in terms of large-scale integration across disciplines, and the involvement of relevant stakeholders, SUNRISE has gathered a strong base of more than 200 supporters, from academia (*ca.*100), industry (55), local research networks and funding agencies. And together, SUNRISE and Energy-X partners and supporters reach the critical mass for research excellence and industrial capabilities in Europe needed to address the challenge to reach a carbon neutral energy system and chemical industry by 2050, as stated in the “[A Clean planet for all](#)” and the “[Green Deal](#)” European long-term strategies. The research initiative will need in the order of 100 M€ per year, to reach the objectives described in the Vision (D1.1) and Roadmap (D1.2). The aim is to reach a significant input of SUNRISE technologies across Europe by 2050.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This blueprint to implement a European large-scale research cooperation working on securing the supply side of the circular economy with renewable fuel and chemicals is a deliverable of SUNRISE CSA with input from its sister CSA Energy-X. It brings together a range of participants from academia, research organisations, society and from the private sector. With this blueprint we urge to complement the scope of existing European partnerships and enable the **full decoupling of economic growth from the utilization of resources** at the local, regional, national and European levels for a sustainable resilient growing economy that leaves no one behind. For the manufacturing of synthetic carbon-neutral hydrocarbons, capturing CO₂ is a major bottleneck. While current public-private partnerships focus on improvements on the demand side with limited impact, SUNERGY proposes **a pipeline of high impact technologies** that boost efficiency **on the supply side** with light-to-products and fuel conversion from atmospheric H₂O, N₂ and CO₂ at high yields with up to **2500 ton/ha.yr CO₂ sequestration for the manufacturing of synthetic carbon-neutral hydrocarbons and including the manufacturing of ammonia and hydrogen or biohydrogen.**

This represents a genuine best effort for Europe, since

- Defossilization of the energy sector on the supply side paves the way for other sectors;
- Why us: we are broad, application oriented, develop technology, and we have vertical integration, science-technology-industry, over the entire knowledge chain;
- There are many national projects, and now it is time to initiate a European partnership to broaden from renewable power from photovoltaics and wind;
- If we do not include this pathway to a low carbon, clean technology economy, we will miss a unique high impact opportunity for the industry in Europe, since energy supply is the largest global market by a wide margin;
- Priority: demonstrate the value chain from source to final product as the single prioritizing criterion;
- By providing a new paradigm we create room for interpretation for other scientific disciplines and for socio-economic stakeholders.

The combination of the SUNRISE and Energy-X initiatives, under the new name SUNERGY, has already received support from over 300 stakeholders all over Europe, and from outside the European continent. This blueprint describes the science and technology (S&T) structure to implement the strategy outlined in the SUNRISE roadmap. It describes how to balance overall project objectives with necessary competences and resources in a transparent process. It takes relevant elements of the Energy-X research agenda on board and builds on a synergistic framework of calls for bottom-up research and innovation actions (RIA) at TRL 0-5, innovation actions (IA), at TRL 6-9, demonstration projects to bridge between the RIA and IA, and demonstrators for dissemination and valorisation in the circular economy. The IA calls will need very strict criteria to maximize their impact, while the RIAs provide the means to nurture new ideas emerging bottom-up from the community. The work is open for new participants and is distributed based on open tenders and a fair selection of the best bids that are put forward in mutual competition by the members of our community and third parties. Resilient short, medium and long-term quality and impact assurance will be implemented to establish credible paths for disruptive change, with innovation pipelines

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delivering plug-in technologies for supplying fuel and chemicals manufactured from renewables at an affordable cost.

The purpose of this deliverable is to map the collaboration and S&T framework, in terms of necessary competencies and resources, including infrastructure aspects, that are needed for an implementation with openness. It provides a mapping of competencies and resources within Europe. The deliverable also considers the parameters for openness in the process of exploitation of results, both in exploiting scientific results with other scientists (Science-to-Science) and in the development of marketable materials, devices and processes (Science-to-Business). We also develop a “call scheme” over the course of 10 years with a number of calls needed to reach the SUNRISE goals. After submitting our blueprint the process will be ‘out of our hands’. Next steps will be that DG Connect will review the outcome and engage in rounds of consultations with EU member states (MS).

1.1. Strategy and practices

The unifying goal of the SUNERGY large-scale initiative is to deliver a steady flow of targeted impact solutions for accelerating the transformation to a scalable energy and supply system. To sustain a circular economy with high economic efficiency, innovative value chains from source to product are needed. The S&T objective of manufacturing fuel and chemicals from abundant molecules in the atmosphere with renewable energy on a meaningful scale to decouple economic growth from utilization of natural resources is articulated in the SUNRISE consolidated vision. The companion strategic roadmap shows how the unifying goal can be realised and what the major milestones are. It situates the large-scale research initiative in the global landscape and identifies four task areas for the technology development of artificial photosynthesis towards societal impact, innovation and exploitation. These are (i) EU-wide massive deployment of sustainably produced hydrogen, (ii) Cost-competitive and decentralised sustainable production of ammonia, (iii) Sustainable carbon capture, and (iv) Cost-competitive and decentralised sustainable production of chemicals and fuels.

The large-scale research initiative will capitalize on the maturity of concentration of electricity from PV and wind, to foster deployment of electrochemical processes, and move forward to the development of innovative technologies enabling the centralized production of ammonia, hydrogen and carbon-based compounds. The scientific underpinning for this part is strengthened by the recent merger of SUNRISE with Energy-X. In addition, the large-scale research initiative will push the development of less mature, visionary photo(electro)chemical, biological and biohybrid systems that will provide the direct decentralized conversion of solar energy into chemical compounds. To reach the highest efficiencies, CO₂ capture and CO₂ activation will have to be integrated in a novel class of high-performance catalytic materials. On the European level the new technologies will provide competitive prices for fuels and compounds that can be concentrated to any desired level, for providing a carbon neutral supply to the circular economy and, ultimately, for enabling the capture and storage of CO₂ from the atmosphere.

The critical step for disruptive technologies is the emergence and growth of innovative value chains. All the high efficiency effort should aim for low investment cost and halving the product price compared to fossil resources. Hence the single prioritizing criterion across the entire S&T

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framework (*i.e.* for both RIAs and IAs alike, as well as for demonstration projects and demonstrators) is the demonstration of the value chain from source to final product. Three global priority research directions (hereafter denoted PRD1, 2, 3) bridging the gap between current capabilities and the unifying visionary goal have been identified as terms of reference for the SUNRISE strategy and practices:

- PRD1: Can we combine water electrolysis with CO₂ capture for realizing fully integrated value chains?
- PRD2: Does integration of steps (PV + electrolysis vs PEC vs molecular vs biological) lead to superior processes in terms of efficiency, selectivity/purity, and concentration over the value chain?
- PRD3: How do we get access to all the hydrogen we need to defossilize our economies?

As innovation stepwise builds on invention, fundamental research, and valorisation, it will be important to create an environment where new concepts and approaches for converting sunlight into fuels and chemicals, developed in academic environments, can be made to harmonize with the drivers that are shaping society. This environment will ultimately depend on established academic networks and public-private partnerships and collaborations. The typical pathway is to have multiple RIA's (*ca* 5 M€ each) with a combination of bottom-up and top-down strategic elements followed by a larger demonstration project partnership (*ca* 10 M€) in a converging approach. A successful demonstration project is based on the best outcome of the preceding RIA stage. Limited redundancy at the RIA stage is used to mitigate risk of failure: successful elements of RIA projects that do not get an independent follow up are included in the demonstration project in a "graceful failure" strategy to build in fault tolerance. Following a go-no go decision, an IA will be the next stage, under top-down programmatic guidance and risk mitigation based on limited redundancy in the IA project plan. While the funding for RIA's will be supplied within the Horizon Europe (HE) framework, for funding the IA's participation of MS and associated countries (AC), with fair compensation for their contributions, will have to provide additional leverage. The mechanisms for compensation will be worked out on a case-by-case basis at the IA proposal stage, and will be subject to contract negotiations with the EU upon selection of the IA for funding prior to its start. In this blueprint, the total cost of the RIAs, demonstration projects, and IAs is initially targeted at *ca* 1.1 billion € from public and private sources. However, it is important to recall that a new energy technology - any new energy technology - requires globally 1 trillion € upfront to bring it to 10 % of its full potential, which should be reached in a time frame of the three decades until 2050. Considering that the European population is 10% the world, a proportional part of these resources, around 100 billion €, will have to be mobilized in due time. Thus, a further growth of a successful research program to a level of 10-20 billion € for the period between 2020-2030 supporting development by the member states and efficient innovation by the private sector, can be envisaged.

The SUNRISE S&T trajectories of RIA's and IAs will feed their results into large demonstrators to push innovation forward in decoupling of economic growth from utilization of resources:

- For pilot scale production of Jet fuel, a 300-500 million revolving fund with airlines is required.
- Pilot scale production for CO₂ capture from concentrated sources, and sequestration of CO₂ from the atmosphere will connect to the ongoing public-private initiatives for innovation in MS and AC.

- For decentralized residential and farming applications geographically distributed demonstration throughout Europe is the preferred action.

Since these demonstrators should operate at the production plant scale, significant funding, *e.g.* from the Green Deal, will be required.

In the view presented in this blueprint, the SUNRISE manufacturers will join the hydrogen valleys, and the demonstrators will lead to new businesses and joint ventures in the new pillar 3 "revolving fund" of HE when they end successfully. This will be equity financed, and not included in the budget for the large-scale research initiative. It is anticipated that a SUNERGY central management will only monitor progress, as the existing demonstrators operate on their own management.

In 2019, the European Commission also announced the launch of the Innovation Fund (IF). This large funding program, as a successor of the NER300 programme, is established by the EU Emission Trading System (EU ETS) Directive for the period 2021 to 2030 and may amount to about 10 billion € depending on the carbon price. The objective is to support the demonstration of highly-innovative low-carbon technologies which can lead to significant emission reductions in Europe. This program will focus on energy intensive industries (including products substituting carbon intensive ones) but also on Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) and Storage (CCS) projects and innovative renewable energy and energy storage technologies, including highly innovative technologies and big flagship projects. The Fund is also open to small-scale projects with total capital costs under €7.5 million. The projects will be selected based on several criteria, *i.e.* the GHG emission reduction potential, degree of innovation, maturity, scalability, cost efficiency.

The Commission aims to launch the first call in 2020 but regular calls are expected until 2030. It is expected that 1.5 billion € will be the total budget of the first IF call mid-2020. This funding program can be an opportunity for demonstration and valorisation of the highest TRL technologies developed within the large-scale research initiative.

2. S&T NETWORKS

2.1 European network of SUNRISE facilities

The SUNRISE initiative will demonstrate source to product value chains in every area of the roadmap with basic, applied and industrial research. The proposed technologies span through a broad range of areas from synthetic chemistry and materials science as well as catalysis, photophysics and photochemistry, molecular biology and biotechnology, via electroengineering to power plant engineering, process technology and energy systems. The academic and engineering resources for the development of SUNRISE technologies cover more or less all academic institutions, and energy or environmental research organizations in Europe. However, not all of these will necessarily have the financial, physical and academic resources to meet the challenge of developing the SUNRISE initiative across all TRLs and on a meaningful scale, up to the level of pilot plants. While the principle challenge at the low TRL stages is to collect bottom-up the "unknown unknowns" with RIA's fostering academic progress, at the higher TRL IA's the emphasis will be on addressing "known unknowns" with strong support from the private sector to forge an efficient programmatic approach over the value chain from source to final product.

A large number of European academic institutions and research organizations are capable of contributing with knowledge and infrastructures, all of them having the experience and willingness

to assume a leading role by building and coordinating international partnerships to perform the RIAs and IAs. The institutions and research organizations will pursue and increase critical mass by promoting new entrants joining the community from all over the globe.

Developing alternative energy carriers and sustainable raw materials is a game changer for today's energy system and for the chemical industry. At the higher TRLs a multidisciplinary, intersectoral, and strongly coordinated effort will be essential to achieve the emergence and growth of innovative value chains. Low investment cost and low product prices compared to fossil resources will require new paradigms for strong economic and systemic drivers in urbanized environments with high economic efficiencies. The fuel market is the world's largest market by far, and the pillars of European industry are highly energy-intensive and rely significantly on the import of crude oil and gas. Beyond 2050, the value chains that derive from the products coming out of the SUNRISE/SUNERGY innovation pipeline should drastically reduce the reliance of the economy on fossil fuels, and shift the international upstream oil and gas market towards renewably produced fuels and chemical feedstocks. This will take cooperativity and strong incentives for this change to become persistent.

SUNRISE technologies create the need for a regional and temporal optimization of supply chains, depending on the availability of resources, such as sunlight, water, CO₂ and N₂ sources. Decentralized SUNRISE solutions thus have to be coupled with existing electric and gas grid infrastructures to guarantee production security and high efficiency in supply chains. In addition, with a diversity of processes and products, additional grid infrastructure is envisaged. This includes dynamic grids for enhanced integration and economic efficiency over the source to product value chain, for instance based on drones, to provide the right amount of resources at the right time and on the right location, and to balance production with demand. A number of local and regional municipal and governmental agencies and companies, that supply infrastructure for energy and water, have expressed their support for SUNRISE, and thereby showed readiness and willingness to comply with future infrastructural needs.

To create a true map of the core networks that SUNRISE can rely on for its development, the organizations and companies that have actively shown support for the SUNRISE and Energy-X initiatives will serve as the nucleus for further growth. These are complemented by cross-cutting organizations, such as KIC InnoEnergy and the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA), that bridge between different communities and support research coordination actions. Together they comprise all technological know-how that can be foreseen as necessary to propel the development according to the SUNRISE roadmap.

The four task areas of the roadmap consist of Sustainable Hydrogen, Sustainable Ammonia, Sustainable Carbon Capture, and Sustainable Chemicals and (Jet) Fuels. In the tables I to IV in the Appendix we present a first overview of organizations SUNRISE has identified that are active in the four areas, starting with SUNRISE and Energy-X supporters, and complemented with organizations from three relevant EERA joint programs, *i.e.* Advanced Materials and Processes for Energy Applications (AMPEA), Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and Fuel Cells and Hydrogen (FCH).

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The organizations listed in the Appendix have taken explicit action to show commitment to participate in one of the above mentioned communities. To start with, during the course of SUNRISE CSA and its preparation we have continuously extended invitations to participate, and the criterion to become a SUNRISE supporter was to write a letter of support that makes credible that the organization can make a contribution. As a next step, the SUNRISE supporters database was extended with parties from the Energy-X research agenda, since those also have shown to be committed by participating in this agenda. Finally, following the DOE we went through the EERA database which also contains organizations that took action to become part of the EERA JP's related to SUNRISE. Finally, we performed a consultation with the SUNRISE supporters on a draft of the blueprint, and used the feedback to finalize the coverage of expertises (section 3) and parties (tables I to IV in the four research areas).

In a large-scale research initiative with openness the community will grow further in the coming years. To support a pipeline of technologies, as presented in this blueprint, an adaptable community is required. This means that a database needs to be maintained continuously in order to be effective. When the follow up of SUNRISE and SUNERGY is secured and maintenance is possible, we will proceed with making the database fully interactive.

3. IDENTIFICATION AND MAPPING OF COMPETENCIES

3.1 Required Competencies and identification of Key Partners

The Partner organizations of SUNRISE, together with the supporting organizations, represent a formidable competence base for carrying out the proposed large-scale project of SUNRISE. Below, we list the required competencies together with key Partners and Supporting Organizations that provide the respective competence. Some additional organizations that are not yet involved in SUNRISE or SUNERGY (a joint SUNRISE/Energy-X initiative, *vide infra*), but have an important competence and have contributed to the SUNRISE Roadmap, are also included. In addition, member organizations of EERA, relevant for the area, are included. Most universities and research institutions have several Key Competencies in the area as of 2020, and with the strong interest in the research area of SUNRISE, the number is growing rapidly. A complete list of organizations is provided in the Appendix.

Catalysis, homogeneous and heterogeneous. Solar fuels and chemicals from small molecules such as water and carbon dioxide require good catalysts that operate at high rate and selectivity, to form pure products at minimum energy cost. Scientific and technical understanding of catalytic reactions and processes are needed to design, evaluate and develop new catalysts that fulfil requirements of performance, durability and scalability.

Competence: Most universities, several research institutions and many companies, such as Johnson Matthey (UK), C&CS catalysts and chemical specialties (DE), Evonik (DE), Haldor Topsoe (DK), InCatT (NL).

Enzymology and Photoenzymology. Enzymes and enzymatic photoconversion cascades are investigated to replace inert expensive metals such as platinum in electrochemical and PEC systems. This is a possible route to reduce cost and increase profit for the generation of hydrogen, ammonia, and manufacturing of hydrocarbons by carbon capture and utilization. The critical hurdle for biotic systems is their robustness over time, and scientific and technical understanding of enzymatic reactions and processes are needed to design, evaluate and develop new conversion cascades and perform microengineering of reactors combining biotic with abiotic components that fulfil requirements of performance, durability and scalability.

Competence: Many universities, such as Barcelona, Cambridge, Freiburg, Leiden, Oxford, Uppsala, Warsaw, York, several research institutions, such as Empa, Fraunhofer, MPI CEC and companies such as H2WIN (BE) and Siemens (DE).

Light-driven processes and reactions. This competence area includes the related but distinct fields of photophysics, photochemistry, natural photosynthesis, photocatalysis and photoelectrochemistry. They provide fundamental scientific knowledge of electronically excited states, charge separation and quantum behaviour in natural photosynthesis, molecules, microorganisms semiconductors, nanoscale and mesoporous systems. This is needed for synthesis and design of molecules, materials and devices, as well as for advanced characterization by experimental and theoretical methods.

Competence: Primarily universities and research institutions, but also companies such as Evonik (DE). Additional companies are found under “(Photo)bioreactors and microbial cultivation”

Electrochemistry. Electrochemistry is essential for electrocatalytic fuel formation, and for their use in fuel cells. It is needed to guide design of materials, devices and systems. Relevant competence is also available in the battery research and industry.

Competence. Most universities and research institutions, as well as many companies, such as Areva H2Gen (FR), Engie (FR), Esy-labs (DE), Hydrogenics (US, BE), Hydron Energy (NL), ITM (UK), Nel (NO), PowerCell (SE), SABIC (NL) and Siemens (DE). Many relevant academic and industrial partners are members of the European initiatives [Battery 2030+](#) and the European Association for Storage of Energy, [EASE](#).

Electrical systems engineering. Several SUNRISE technologies (electrolyzers; photoelectrochemical systems) depend on complex systems that include electrical and electronic components.

Competence. Many universities, research institutions and several companies, such as CEGASA (ES), Engie (FR), RWE (DE) and Siemens (DE).

Solar energy technologies. Current solar energy technologies include photovoltaics, CSP, and solar thermal technologies. SUNRISE technology development will benefit from synergies with this sector. This includes production, deployment and operation of systems and components.

Competence. Many universities and research institutions, and companies such as SUNRISE partners and supporters ENGIE (FR), Proheat Heattrace (ES, UK), PVH_Energy Storage (ES), Siemens (DE),

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Synthesis and characterization of molecules and materials. Preparation of materials and components is an obvious need for SUNRISE.

Competence. This is a core competence at essentially every university and research institution involved in chemical and materials research. The chemical and materials industry is also very strong in the EU, organized through e.g. EMIRI, EuChemS and the EERA Joint Program AMPEA. Examples include additional SUNRISE Partners and Supporters, such as Johnson-Matthay (UK), Arkema France (FR), Avantium (NL), 3M, Spain (ES), Clariant (CH), Covestro (DE), Cristal Global (UK), Everest Coatings (NL), NOVAMONT (IT), Sulapac (FI)

Chemical, Materials and Process Engineering. For production of components and modules for the SUNRISE technology systems, as well as for the handling of products, engineering is required.

Competence. Many universities and research institutions, and companies such as Certech (BE), DECHEMA (DE), Plasmatechnologie GmbH (DE), Plasmatreat GmbH (DE), Dr Laure Plasmatechnologie (DE),

Membranes. Most design concepts for gaseous solar fuel formation include a membrane for separation of product gases, e.g. hydrogen or syngas from oxygen. At the same time, the membrane should allow for rapid proton transport from anode to cathode.

Competence. Several universities and research institutions, as well as European companies such as Solvay-Solexis (FR), Polymem S.A (FR) and Fumatech/Dupont de Nemours (FR) (membranes producers) and e.g. Axane (FR), Symbio FC (FR), Renault (FR), Toyota (J, BE) (end-users). The EERA Joint Programme AMPEA, and Fuel Cells and Hydrogen (FCH-JU) gather competence in the area.

Carbon dioxide Capture and Utilization. Capture of carbon dioxide from flue gas or ambient air is the first step in the cycle of carbon dioxide conversion to fuels and chemicals. Current prospects for direct air capture would result in large energy losses for the CO₂ capture and concentration. SUNRISE aims to drastically reduce those energy losses by novel concepts. By direct coupling of CO₂ capture to catalysis, optimally matching the CO₂ flow and photocatalytic reactions, thermodynamic losses can be minimized. This requires more research on new concepts.

CO₂ capture from point sources, such as industrial emissions, can significantly reduce the carbon footprint of major industrial sectors. The competences of many stakeholders are needed for the transition to a circular and CO₂ neutral economy.

Competence. A large number of companies are active in this area, including Aker solutions (NO), Antecy (NL), ArcelorMittal (LU), BASF (DE), Carbyon (NL), CRI_Carbon Recycling International (IS), Climeworks (CH), ENGIE (FR), Ineratec (DE), H2WIN (BE), KT-Kinetics Technology SPA (IT), Lhoist (BE), Linde Engineering (DE), Liquid Wind (SE), Quantis Sàrl (CH), RWE (DE), Siemens (DE), Skytree (NL), Solvay (BE), Stena (SE) and ZEG Power A.S. (NO). [CO₂ Value Europe](#) is an organization for companies, universities and organizations active in the area of carbon capture and utilization. The [EERA Joint Programme Carbon Capture and Storage](#) is another one.

Water and air management. This is focused on the processes of chemically scrubbing carbon dioxide from industrial exhaust gasses, directly from ambient air, or from seawater. In addition, water is needed for water-splitting reactions of large-scale solar fuels technology, and the quality of water needs to be matched to the technological requirements. To achieve this in an efficient and economically viable manner, expertise is needed on emission detection technologies and the removal of contaminants from exhaust gas flows and the maritime environment.

Competence. Canal de Isabel II (ES), PlasmaAir AG (DE)

Genetic and metabolic engineering of microorganisms; synthetic biology, biotechnology. Genetic and metabolic approaches are widely used today to re-design microorganisms for efficient production of targeted solar fuels and chemicals. Synthetic metabolic pathways can be inserted into microorganisms to allow for production of the fuel or chemical of choice. Biotechnology methods are enablers of this development.

Competence. Many universities and research institutions. Companies with competence directed towards solar fuels include Cyano Biotech (DE), Photanol (NL), H2WIN (BE) INGENZA (UK), Neste (FI) and PEPperPRINT (DE).

Computational chemistry/physics. Advanced theoretical chemistry and physics tools for computational investigation of the properties of molecules and materials including their dynamic structure are essential for materials discovery and characterization, elucidating reaction mechanisms in chiral systems etc.

Competence. Most universities and research institutions, as well as several companies, including SCM Amsterdam (NL).

Multiscale modelling. Solar fuels devices and systems need to integrate processes occurring on many different time- and length scales, from femtoseconds to days and from the nano- and mesoscale to at least several meters. Substrates and products in liquid and/or gaseous form need to be provided, transported and collected; electrons and protons need to be transferred, and transported, concentration gradients handled etc. Multi-scale simulations are vital for the design and analysis on both the device and the systems level, and an engineering theory for the bottom-up design of modular device concepts is urgently needed.

Competence. Several universities, research institutions and companies. The EERA AMPEA Joint Programme has a sub-programme dedicated to multiscale modelling of materials, processes and devices and gathers some of the key European actors in the field. There are also two European centres of Excellence gathering key European actors: [MAX](#) (MAterials design at the eXascale) and [EoCoE](#) (Energy Oriented Center of Excellence)

Informatics, AI. Bioinformatics is an important tool for understanding biological data. It can be used *e.g.* in the analysis of gene and protein expression and regulation, or to optimize metabolic pathways. Informatics, machine learning and Artificial intelligence (AI) will become more important in the near future also for *e.g.* materials discovery.

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Competence. Several universities, research institutions and companies. The two above-mentioned centres of excellence MAX (MAterials design at the eXascale) and EoCoE (Energy Oriented Center of Excellence) are active in this field with key European actors.

Information technology. A large-scale research and development project requires strong IT solutions. Prototypes, demonstration and the final technology will need constant and remote monitoring of operation.

Competence. Several companies, including SUNRISE supporter PCM Technology Solutions (UK).

Handling of fuels. This includes handling, conversion (*e.g.* syngas-to-C_n compounds, H₂-formate interconversion), storage and transportation of gaseous and liquid fuels. The processes should be optimized for both small scale production of solar fuels on *e.g.* house roofs as well as for large-scale production of jet fuels.

Competence. Gas and oil companies, which are strongly represented in Europe, *e.g.* Shell (NL), TOTAL S.A. (FR), HyGear B.V. (NL), Linde (DE), Neste (FI), Repsol (ES), ST1 (FI) and ENAGAS (ES). R&D on fuel and chemicals interconversion processes involves several universities and research institutes.

Fertilizers. For deployment of fertilizers produced by SUNRISE technologies, companies that produce and distribute fertilizers today are key partners.

Competence. European companies include BASF (DE), Casale (CH), Stamicarbon (NL), Tara (NO) and Thyssenkrupp (DE).

(Photo)Bioreactors and microbial cultivation. Bioreactor and photobioreactor competence, and competence in cultivation of photosynthetic microorganisms, is needed for design and operation of large-scale production of solar fuels and solar chemicals. The competence is valuable for photoreactor design, also with non-biological approaches

Competence. Universities and research institutes, and European companies such as Ecoduna Eparella GmbH (AT), Photanol (NL), Subitec (DE), AlgoSource (FR), Algae for Future (A4F, PT), Electroarchea (DE).

Transportation. A major future end user of the SUNRISE technology products is the transportation sector, including personal and heavy ground vehicles, ships and air planes.

Competence. European companies are particularly strong in the transportation sector. This includes transportation companies, and vehicle and component manufacturing companies, such as SUNRISE supporters Copenhagen Airports, Toyota Motor Europe (BE), Fev GmbH (DE), Marion Technologies S.A (FR), Schaeffler (DE), Stena Line/Stena Rederi (SE).

Energy systems. When consumers and industries produce and exchange solar fuels and solar chemicals, new energy distribution systems and regulations have to be developed and put into place. To optimally integrate the use of renewables into existing networks, smart grids technology needs

to be developed further, supported by information technology, policy regulations and market instruments.

Competence. Major European companies include the SUNRISE partners and supporters ENGIE (FR), Acconia (ES), CIC Energigune (ES), EDP Energia (ES), ENDESA (ES), Fortum Power and Heat Oy (FI), HUNOSA (ES), Petrogal SA (PT) and Uniper (DE). The [EERA Joint Programme Energy Systems Integration](#) also gathers many key European actors in the field.

Device and systems engineering. Devices, processes, and systems need to be optimized based on lab scale Proof-of-Concepts to lab-scale demos for making fuel from CO₂ and sunlight on a house roof. In parallel, large-scale Proof-of-Concepts will be obtained for running pilot production of jet fuel and further scale up at industrial sites. This includes computational design of devices considering e.g. fluid dynamics, heat management etc. as well as building hardware.

Competence. Several universities and research institutions, as well as many Companies, such as the SUNRISE partners and supporters Siemens (DE), Engie (FR) Atmostat-Alcen (FR).

Construction. Large-scale deployment of solar technologies will need the competence of construction companies.

Competence. Many European companies, such as SUNRISE supporter LafargeHolcim (FR)

Innovation, entrepreneurship. Research and innovation needs to be brought to products and the market. While several SMEs emerge active in solar fuel technology for small scale production on house roofs, farms and private gardens, the scale of the future solar fuels system demands involvement also of large companies.

Competence. Several technical Universities and Research Institutions have strong innovation competence. Several large companies are active in areas relevant for solar fuels: oil & gas (see above), energy technology (e.g. Siemens, Engie), materials (JM). Economic development agencies such as Innovation Quarter (NL) are needed to stimulate regional collaboration and implementation strategies.

Environmental and sustainability aspects, Life-cycle assessment (LCA) and techno-economic analyses (TEA). Analysis of climate and other environmental impact, as well as sustainability, is vital for development and implementation of energy technologies. LCA is a standard tool to assess environmental impacts associated with all the stages of the life-cycle of a commercial product, process, or service. Life Cycle Energy Assessment (LCEA) is important to estimate the Energy Return on Energy Invested (EROI). For emerging technologies, it is important to develop predictive LCA together with techno-economic analyses as well as social aspects such as assessing public acceptance.

Competence. Several Universities and Research Institutions, as well as Companies, such as NOVATLANTIS (CH), Metabolic (NL), and several others.

Recycling and circular processes. This includes the activities and actions required to reuse product materials and manage waste streams in a circular manner, including the collection, transport,

sorting, re-use and recycling of waste, supported by circular policy regulations and circular business models.

Competence. Companies focusing on recycling and circular industrial processes include EcoRecycling SRL (IT) and Nextchem – Maire Tecnimont (IT).

Outreach, Education and Public acceptance. New energy technologies need public acceptance for large-scale implementation. The SUNRISE technologies imply wide deployment of light harvesting infrastructures and new industrial facilities for production and distribution of fuels and chemicals, along with conversion of existing petrochemical facilities. Availability of raw materials for the new processes and facilities also needs to be carefully addressed. An industrial transformation of this size inevitably implies social and economic impact on a large scale. In case of success, such changes will be strongly beneficial for society, but this is not immediately obvious to citizens! Therefore, a substantial amount of human and financial resources needs to be mobilized to promote scientifically-grounded information on the vast industrial transformation. This needs to be handled very carefully, especially in a time when unscientific beliefs quickly spread across the web, particularly through social media. Every partner involved has to support a strong outreach and educational plan – also involving interaction with social sciences and humanities – in order to promote the SUNRISE technologies at all level of the educational system, *i.e.* all the way from elementary school to universities, as well as to involve the society at large and mass media professionals in particular.

Competence. All universities and research Institutions, as well as several companies, have dedicated technical staff and even research personnel dedicated to education and outreach. Fruitful interactions with existing initiatives can be envisaged, for instance with KIC InnoEnergy, Climate-KIC and KIC Raw materials, which are funded by the EU through the EIT.

Legislative aspects, policy making, financing. Apart from a large-scale research initiative additional actions need to be implemented such as leveraging research and innovation funding from both the private sector as well as MS/AC investments. At present, EU RTD schemes do rarely go beyond the demonstration stage. For subsequent innovation steps, the much higher efficiency of the private sector compared to academia and research institutions is essential to nurture rapid progress. However, ambitious investments need to be financed if they are to be successful, and the supply of the enormous financial resources that are required upfront by the private R&D stakeholders in small scale financing operations is unrealistic. The only sector of the financial system that has in principle the capacity to finance an energy innovation effort is the global bond market. While this is globally the biggest source of capital, bonds are low yield, low risk financial instruments. To finance high risk innovation trajectories with green bonds, the EU and member state governments can implement derisking mechanisms were the state backs the risk to release the necessary financial resources on the required scale, following China that has taken the lead in greening its financial system already.¹ An important conclusion is that *ca* 15% of the financial resources can come from public, *i.e.* tax-based resources, with the remaining 85% of needed funding coming from the private sector. With a large-scale research initiative funded on the European level with 1 billion € from public sources,

¹ <https://www.cbd.int/financial/privatesector/china-Green%20Task%20Force%20Report.pdf>

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about 10-20 € billion will be needed from private sources for the period of 2020-2030, and around 80 billion € between 2030 and 2050.

Green bonds are on their way to becoming mainstream in tapping the immense investment potential of the financial markets.² Asian countries like Korea and also European member states like the Netherlands have demonstrated that institutional investors, pension funds and insurance funds, which have between them over 60 trillion € in investable funds and where capital shortage is not a problem, are willing to purchase green securities at investment grade from respectable banks. This will make the financing of aggregates of projects at low capital cost possible by low interest rates. It will allow governments to address the financing directly without any intermediaries, in contrast with carbon tax financing measures. By providing backing, governments put their credibility at stake to finance genuine green deals, since investors will perform due diligence and markets will immediately react in case of inefficiencies in the implementation and penalize the issuer of the bonds. Displacing fossil resources by renewables then becomes a government driven private investment, rather than a tax financed cost of mitigation.

In addition, legislative aspects such as liability and de-risking needs to be addressed, *e.g.* for the cross-national utilization of abundant resources (water, air) and in particular their potential pollution.

Competence. The EC and National Governments, as well as SUNRISE supporter organizations (*e.g.* WWF, EuCheMS, CO2 Value Europe, Fonden Teknologi (DK) and the Green-Win collaboration.

3.2 Infrastructure needs

a) Access to large (regional, national and trans-national) infrastructure is needed for the SUNRISE projects. Towards this need, ESFRI has a mission to support a coherent and strategy-led approach to policy-making on research infrastructures in Europe, and to facilitate multilateral initiatives leading to the better use and development of research infrastructures, at EU and international levels.

- Laser spectroscopy is key to investigate light-induced excited state processes in solar fuel components, materials and devices. [Laserlab Europe](#) is an Integrated Initiative of European Laser Research Infrastructures in 18 countries. This builds on European strength in the area to offer [transnational access](#) to top-quality laser research facilities in a highly co-ordinated fashion for the benefit of the European research community.
- Development of artificial photosynthesis reaction cascades critically depends on biomimetic nanotechnologies that lower transition states along adiabatic or nonadiabatic reaction coordinates by tuning of their ground state dynamic structure. Hybrid structure determination by computational integration of **cryo-EM**, **electron diffraction**, **solid state NMR** and other spectroscopic methods require state of the art infrastructure at the national

² Global Green Shift: When Ceres Meets Gaia (2017) J.A. Mathews, Anthem Press, ISBN1783086408

and European level. Many countries have state of the art EM and NMR infrastructures in place that will contribute to the structural underpinning and provide mechanistic insight.

- Current researchers on solar fuels are already important users at **synchrotrons and free-electron laser (FEL) facilities**, and have to a large extent helped motivate the investment in FELs. There are several synchrotrons with top-class performance within MS and AC, and two FELs (out of five in the world) are in Europe, in Hamburg and in Switzerland. [LEAPS](#) – the League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources – is a strategic consortium initiated by the Directors of the Synchrotron Radiation and Free Electron Laser user facilities in Europe.
- **Neutron scattering facilities** are also important, with several sources within EU. The European Neutron Scattering Association ([ENSA](#)) is an affiliation of national neutron scattering societies and committees, which directly represent users. The European Spallation Source (ESS) is currently under construction in south Sweden and will be the world's most powerful neutron source.
- **High-performance computing centers** are already used for both theoretical and computational chemistry and physics of molecules and materials, simulations and multi-scale modelling. Analysis of large amounts of experimental data, including data mining and meta-analysis also depends on high-performance computing. As AI and machine learning becomes more important, computing is expected to become more efficient; nevertheless, it is highly likely that computing demands will increase in the future.
- **Testing and certification centres**, as for *e.g.* photovoltaics, will have to be established also for solar fuels, *e.g.* the Helmholtz Energy Materials Foundry (HEMF). This will allow for rational comparison of systems and for certifying performance. However, standardisation of conditions is significantly more complicated than for solar cells, as substrate (feedstock) needs to be provided and different products need to be extracted.
- **Pilot and demonstration plants** need to be built, and because of their large-scale, funding from the private sector will be important.
- **Databases** and facilitated access will be important tools. The Pasteur Culture Collection (Paris) and Nordic Culture Collection (NordAqua, FI) provide high-quality biological material for the generation of reliable scientific results and technological innovations. This includes a large collection of photosynthetic cyanobacteria. There are many databases of materials, for example, [NRELMatDB](#) is a computational materials database with the specific focus on materials for renewable energy applications including, but not limited to, photovoltaic materials, materials for photo-electrochemical water splitting, thermoelectrics, etc. The main goal of NRELMatDB is to enable and facilitate the access and exchange of computational data between different research groups following the guidelines outlined in the Presidential Materials Genome Initiative. With the development of SUNRISE, there will be a need for developing materials databases comprising the research and technology needs of this field.

EERA has summarized existing databases comprising infrastructure in their report: “[Sharing data, research infrastructure: summary report](#)”. The Joint Programs AMPEA, CCS and Fuel cells and hydrogen are the most relevant ones in the context of SUNRISE.

b) Local and regional large-scale infrastructure is also important, in the form of expensive experimental equipment (e.g. clean rooms, sterile rooms, advanced microscopy and spectroscopy resources, state-of-the-art bioreactors etc.) and computer clusters. This type of equipment is available in multiple copies over Europe, on a frequent basis to serve local and regional users.

4. OPENNESS OF THE INITIATIVE

4.1 Governance structure overview

As the Flagship partnership model is no longer an option, efforts of the governance team in SUNRISE are dedicated to exploring instruments and options (partnerships, missions) in the context of the next Framework Programme Horizon Europe (HE), in order to build a tentative scenario for launching a Large-scale European Research and Innovation Initiative (LSERI). All this is done in close collaboration with the CSA project ENERGY-X, with which SUNRISE has agreed to form a new, large-scale initiative called SUNERGY. All aspects of the new initiative are under discussion, including governance schemes. A partnership is presently the favoured option on the long term for SUNERGY, on the basis of which a scenario and timeline with intermediate steps has been built. In the long term of this scenario, which can be found in Deliverable 4.1, the SUNERGY partnership will be: “Fossil-free fuels, chemicals and materials for a circular economy (3FCM)”. A co-programmed European public-private partnership (cPPP) appears as the most appropriate structure. However, the existing partnership schemes are limited from the point of view of financial leverage and from an efficiency perspective. Up to H2020, the EU programmes have stopped at the demonstration stage. With the advent of pillar 3 in HE, with equity financed innovation this is going to change. When institutional investors, pension funds and insurance investors participate in innovation based on due diligence, a high efficiency will be required to drive innovation. There are no adequate governance schemes yet for this purpose, which requires much stricter top-down governance than what is usually applied in settings with academic freedom to accumulate knowledge.

1.

Figure 1: Tentative scenario and timeline for the SUNERGY large-scale European research and innovation initiative.

A team consisting of members from both SUNRISE and ENERGY-X have met and discussed an outline of a SUNERGY governance model and built tentative scenarios and the related timeline to have this SUNERGY co-programmed partnership starting in 2024. This is illustrated in Figure 1. The group identified the need to create a common academic board for SUNERGY, having a balanced composition from members from SUNRISE and ENERGY-X, as well as an industrial board, yet ensuring a global consistency of each board in terms of composition taking into account, whenever possible, aspects such as the types of organizations, the geographical distribution of members and gender. The two boards are, briefly:

- **Scientific executive board:** this board is responsible for the operational running of SUNERGY in this intermediate period with members having different roles and tasks which can be delegated whenever needed.
- **Industrial board:** the independent industrial board, separate from the scientific executive board, was deemed necessary to keep independency but at the same time working in close interaction together. The industrial board would have as a main role to bring the views of industry for the overall development and strategy of SUNERGY.

In addition to these, a strategic advisory board with a controlling function should also be appointed to give an external advice on the evolution of SUNERGY.

4.2 Openness in the governance structure of SUNRISE or SUNERGY

Openness in the initiative means both in respect to transparency of the organization and its governance, as well as the partnership being open for stakeholders to take part in the work. A major criticism against previous Flagships were the lack of openness in the available opportunities to participate in the work. SUNRISE seeks to avoid any situation which may limit or hamper open

research and the rapid development of technology, by making sure that a future partnership will be open for all competitive initiatives

Openness to participation:

The activities of the future SUNERGY initiative will aim for creating the best possible environment for research and innovation for SUNRISE technologies. The SUNERGY partnership will prepare or support a multi-annual work programme for the SUNERGY Large-scale European Research Initiative (LSERI) with a series of calls; proposals for specific instruments for SMEs and start-ups could be part of this programme (liaison with the European Innovation Centre, EIC). These calls will be an instrument which is open for all stakeholders, provided that they are eligible for funding under the HE Work Programme, and is under the administrative control of the European Commission. The calls will be based on the SUNERGY roadmap, itself resulting from the merging of the roadmaps of SUNRISE and ENERGY-X, both roadmaps being the result of an open consultation with all stakeholders. The selected projects at these open calls will have a collaboration agreement with SUNERGY, *i.e.* its coordination activities as well as with all the other selected projects, in order to allow a monitoring and revision of the roadmap, again in an open process with the SUNERGY community. Furthermore, the partnership will work on a pragmatic contractual framework for the LSERI including questions on IP management, access to research results and rules for fair compensation of academic IP.

Transparency of the partnership:

To ensure openness and transparency, which is essential for enabling accountability and trust in the initiative, several mechanisms can be employed:

a) *Strategic Advisory Board*

A Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) can provide advice for strategic decision-making to the two boards (scientific and industrial). An SAB can provide feedback to the SUNERGY strategic research and innovation agenda, and monitor the initiative's progress towards its research, innovation, and commercialization goals, as well as education and outreach. The SAB should also include members representing the civil society. An SAB would also be able to propose Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the output and impact, and evaluate these on a regular basis. For these reasons SUNERGY will evaluate the possibility of having an SAB separate from the programming board in the future partnership governance scheme. The programming board would associate mandated expert members of the public and private stakeholders plus a funding board with representatives of EC and MS and ACs and would act as the main liaison body with the public partners and the coordination and implementation part of SUNERGY. The SAB would have an advising role with the EC and MS and the programming on the evolution and performance of the partnership. Further details can be found in the deliverables D4.1 and D4.2.

b) *Dissemination and communication*

Dissemination and communication with stakeholders, the broader scientific community, policy makers and the civil society needs a clear strategy and good coordination among communication and dissemination of related/initiated projects (*e.g.* organisation of an annual conference for

relevant projects, newsletters, etc.) as well as for the executive boards, is critical for openness and trust in the initiative. More details are given in the SUNRISE Deliverable 3.1.

5. INVESTMENT SCENARIO

5.1 Comprehensive description for the priority research and implementation directions

Putting Europe's energy supply on a path to a sustainable future while leaving no one behind requires solving complex S&T challenges on the supply side. Figure 2 shows schematically how a commercially viable solar fuel can emerge which combines the almost infinite potential of solar energy with the versatility of hydrocarbon fuels. This figure summarizes the technology readiness (horizontally indicated with shades of green according to the vertical scale on the right) of innovation pipelines (vertical single and double arrows) for (bio)hydrogen, biofuels, electric power, and synthetic carbon-neutral hydrocarbons. TRLs range from 0 (white, center) to 9 (dark green, outer parts). The 1st generation biofuels with crops, and 2nd generation biomass and gasification for biofuels and biohydrogen are proven technologies. The 3rd generation biofuels and biohydrogen from algae are TRL 4-6, and 4th generation with synthetic biology pathways for direct conversion is under development at low TRL 1-3. On the right hand side the dark green fields connected by horizontal arrows depict the high TRL value chain of generation of renewable electricity from PV and wind for power that feeds into electrolysis for hydrogen production and hydrocarbon synthesis (Fischer Tropsch). Partial integration with thermolysis and photoelectrolysis (PEC) for hydrogen feeds into hydrocarbon synthesis are both at intermediate TRL. For the manufacturing of synthetic carbon-neutral hydrocarbons, capturing CO₂ is a major bottleneck. While CO₂ capture from concentrated sources is at intermediate TRL, CO₂ air capture and CO₂ activation are low TRL. Benefits are expected from integration of CO₂ air capture with activation (indicated with overlapping text blocks), and further integration with advanced and novel synthesis methods, presently at intermediate TRL, for the manufacturing of synthetic carbon-neutral hydrocarbons. The “artificial leaf” at the center combines the best of both worlds via biomimicry and nanotechnology (dashed horizontal arrows), both for hydrogen and for synthetic carbon neutral hydrocarbons and is at the lowest TRL. Horizontal arrows indicate existing connections (solid contours) or expected connections (dashed contours)

Figure 2. The broad field of technologies from biofuel to renewable power, and their TRLs (schematic). The large-scale research initiative is indicated with a dashed contour and covers the technologies ranging from (A) advanced biotech with synthetic biology, (B) the visionary “artificial leaf” based on advances in life sciences and nanotechnology in the center, and on the right (C) synthesis with activated CO₂ and (D) direct conversion with photoelectrolysis (PEC) or thermolysis, and conventional conversion of renewable electricity with electrolysis. Arrows A, B and D address PRD3, how to obtain all the hydrogen to decarbonize our economies. Arrow C concerns PRD1, how to combine water electrolysis with CO₂ capture. Finally, with arrows A,B, and C will be determined to what extent integration of steps gives better processes in terms of efficiency, selectivity and concentration over the value chain, i.e. PRD2. Adapted from [Purchase et al., DOI: 10.1142/9789813274440_0003](https://doi.org/10.1142/9789813274440_0003)

5.1.1. The Science and Technology Case

The principle S&T challenge for SUNERGY is to find the technically novel optimal value chain(s) to combine the benefits of biofuels (*i.e.* a renewable hydrocarbon fuel) with the ‘unlimited’ availability of renewable electricity. The existing route to manufacture fuel and chemicals from atmospheric CO₂ is via biomass, and it provides roughly 10% of the world’s primary energy supply. The existing 1st and 2nd generation source to product value chains on the biological side are well in line with the three priority research directions of this blueprint. First, biology already combines water splitting with the capture of atmospheric CO₂. Second, functional requirements (such as light absorption, water splitting and CO₂ conversion) have led to evolutionary selection of carefully engineered subcellular responsive matrix cascades (protein complexes, membranes, organelles) with sizes, reaction rates, and energetic properties optimized at internal interfaces for high yield, selectivity and concentration of energy. Third, in nature electrons and protons are separated, but never far apart, and hydrogen ions are available to generate biohydrogen or react with CO₂ for manufacturing hydrocarbons. However, while modern biomass technology is affordable and can be sustainable, the current as well as projected supply of biomass is insufficient to meet the need for

fuel and chemicals. Additionally, biomass production for energy purposes will inevitably be limited by the boundaries imposed by required food supply and ecosystem services. This is why a separate large-scale research initiative is required.

With its comprehensive synergistic portfolio of technologies, SUNERGY provides justifiably high hopes for forging the tools for concentration and conversion of energy with a pipeline of high impact technologies that are scalable, affordable and sustainable, and can boost the supply side with light-to-products and fuel conversion from atmospheric CO₂ at high yields up to 2500 ton/ha p.a. In arrow block A, organisms will be tailored with synthetic biology for direct biosynthesis of biohydrogen and carbon-neutral hydrocarbons. This 4th generation direct conversion will have better efficiency, selectivity/purity, and concentration over source to product value chains than 1st, 2nd and 3rd generation processes. On the other end of the technology spectrum there is renewable electricity for power, with electrolysis, thermolysis and photoelectrolysis in block D providing hydrogen for the synthesis of hydrocarbons from CO₂ in block C. The source to - hydrogen - product value chain at highest TRL in D is conventional electrolysis from renewable power. However, a significant reduction of CAPEX is necessary to contribute to providing all the hydrogen we need. The more integrated hydrogen supply routes with direct photoelectrolysis or thermolysis in D can give better efficiency than conventional electrolysis, but further development is needed to raise the TRL. To decarbonize with *e.g.* Fischer Tropsch for hydrocarbon synthesis, the hydrogen from electrolysis, photoelectrolysis or thermolysis needs to be combined or integrated in C with capturing and activation of atmospheric CO₂, which is still a distant promise. For the CO₂ conversion in C, centralized point sources will be compared with decentralized integrated CO₂ capture and activation, and integration with novel and advanced hydrocarbon synthesis. R&D into new classes of advanced non-adiabatic biomimetic responsive matrix nanotechnology cascades in B inspired by photosynthesis, “the artificial leaf”, is a vibrant area of low TRL, high impact research to determine if extensive integration of steps gives better processes in terms of efficiency, selectivity and concentration over the value chain.

5.1.2 Efficiency is key for the demonstration of source to final product value chains

According to the first law of thermodynamics, energy can neither be created, nor destroyed. So why do we bother about it so much? This is because of the second law, which states that every time energy is converted or concentrated, it becomes less useful, until in the end only entropy is left, thermal energy that is unavailable for doing useful work. While fossil resources have been slowly concentrated on a geological time scale in the earth’s crust, renewables such as solar and wind are dilute and need conversion and concentration into fuels and chemicals that can be stored and handled for further use on the time scales of humans: a night, for days, seasonal storage, up to years. The higher the concentration, the faster the conversion, and the longer the storage time, the more entropy is produced.

The purpose of PRD2 is to determine to what extent integration of steps gives better processes in terms of efficiency, selectivity and concentration over the value chain. Air transport and heavy industry require large amounts of energy at specific locations, while for decentralized applications better efficiencies are obtained by avoiding too much concentration and subsequent dilution, balancing generation with demand over different locations and over time instead, and avoiding complex multi-step conversion networks as much as possible by converting renewables directly to

the form in which they will be used. Since renewables are dilute by definition, their supply is more a concentration problem than anything else. Electric concentration of energy appears easy and looks attractive, but as a consequence also raw materials need to be concentrated, including CO₂ from the atmosphere. When CO₂ capture and CO₂ activation are integrated in one material, the higher efficiencies are obtained at lower rates. Exactly at thermodynamic equilibrium, there is no conversion and the losses for atmospheric CO₂ concentration vanish. In contrast, for combining CO₂ with conventional water electrolysis at high current density (PRD1) also high CO₂ conversion rates will be required, and typically half of the free energy will have to be spent on CO₂ concentration alone. For decentralized applications as with PEC, current densities are low, with less CO₂ concentration losses compared to centralized conversion. This is a strong argument against combining CO₂ capture with conventional electrolysis and in favour of decentralized direct air capture and conversion (DACC) with integrated PEC or artificial leaf technology. It is thus for good reasons that research attention internationally is shifting from conventional electrolysis to PEC and molecular systems, which can produce the required paradigm shift and impact on the supply side our economies are looking for.

For the demonstration of source to final product value chains at the best price, efficiency is key. It should be emphasized that for light to fuels and chemicals conversion the most important is to actually use incoming photons well, and therefore we consider *photon to product yields* of at least 70% as leading. Another way of stating this is: don't waste more than 30% of the incoming light, on reflections, internal recombination losses, side paths, light colour changes in the morning and in the evening, and so on. The critical technological hurdle in the development is to overcome the recombination losses, and develop nanostructured photoreactor cascades that can sustain 16 mA/cm² tandem photocurrent into product, in the laboratory under AM1.5 irradiation. The *energy efficiencies* follow from the yield. The thermodynamic optimum for photochemical energy storage is realized with integrated tandem photochemical cells, where every electron transported into the product requires two incoming photons. The 70% photon to hydrogen product yield then corresponds with a solar to hydrogen *energy efficiency* of 30%. Hydrogen is the most favourable case. There is, however, one other caveat: this should not lead to detrimental materials efficiencies to slow down conversion rates, as this generates entropy. In addition, large quantities of materials increase cost, especially when such materials are not very abundant in the earth's crust.

For many years scientists have been running up against a wall to achieve high energy efficiency *and* high yield *and* high materials efficiency simultaneously. Very recently, however, science has learned from natural photosynthesis how to achieve this. In the existing energy conversion technology the electrons are considered to be in equilibrium with their atomic surroundings and reactions are mostly probabilistic events. Natural systems do it differently, in the sense that proteins apparently can break the second law of thermodynamics temporarily with quantum instabilities (Figure 3). Since quantum networks are deterministic instead of probabilistic and self-select the fastest channel to the product, they form an attractive engineering concept for tailoring source to product value chains. With access to responsive matrices based on biomimicry and nanotechnology, extensive integration of steps to provide enhanced efficiency and better selectivity while keeping energy concentrated along the reaction cascades can become reality. This is the fundamental breakthrough for lowering the cost relative to current practice, since recent fundamental work has provided converging and convincing evidence that near-unity yields can indeed be achieved in man-made quantum conversion systems.

Figure 3. (a, from Energy-X) In adiabatic conversions, reactants A and B are on a catalyst surface that lowers the activation barrier. With the catalyst the reaction proceeds in steps along the reaction coordinate, driven over the barriers by e.g. thermal fluctuations or an electron motive force. Along the way, there are intermediate states until at the end the product is formed. The reactant, intermediates and product states are separated by energy barriers, the transition states. Along the entire path, the reactants are kept in equilibrium with the atomic surrounding in the catalyst with the driving force applied. (b, from SUNRISE) nonadiabatic reactions in - preferably chiral - responsive matrices proceed along a quantum reaction coordinate Q . Along the reaction coordinate sudden events occur, such as absorption of light, or release of protons, that trigger a rapid twisting response of the atomic surrounding that is nonadiabatic, i.e. too fast for the electrons to follow. When a reactant state is swept over a product state by a responsive matrix, a gap opens up, which is a well-known phenomenon known as avoided crossing. By coupling to a vibration from the environment, the reactant is converted into the product by quantum coherent tunneling through the barrier instead of over the barrier, and the tunneling channel closes afterwards. Since back reaction is prevented this way, the quantum mechanism breaks the time reversal symmetry and thereby the second law of thermodynamics that is rooted in time reversal symmetry.

In the roadmap presented by SUNRISE and the list of activities below, the efficiency is increased in steps:

1. Good efficiency can be obtained with electrochemical processes in bulk materials, where there are overpotential losses at the PV side and at the catalysis side. These systems use bulk materials. The CO_2 capture potential is limited to 1500 t/ha p.a due to high concentration losses on the CO_2 side.
2. Better efficiency is obtained with photoelectrochemical (PEC) direct conversion since the losses from the PV stage and the catalysis stage are under one overpotential, thus eliminating the need for a second one. These systems also use bulk materials. The estimated CO_2 capture potential is ca. 2000 t/ha p.a. since CO_2 concentration losses are alleviated compared to conventional (co-)electrolysis at high current density.
3. The best materials efficiencies are accessible through photochemical materials, bioinspired, biological or biohybrid, that eliminate the electronic current intermediate by switching from bulk materials to molecules. This leads to the best materials efficiency, with CO_2 capture potential up to 2500 t/ha p.a. for fully developed non-adiabatic direct conversion tandem systems that can sustain 16 mA/cm^2 (AM 1.5) photocurrent into products.

The power of a pipeline for optimal economic efficiency while respecting our moral freedom

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We want to domesticate energy, on our roofs, for our comfort and wellbeing, but not end up energy domesticating us or lead us into another era of neo-colonialism because of terrestrial requirements exceeding the capabilities of Europe. SUNRISE technologies will not compete with agriculture and have a high solar energy conversion efficiency, potentially reaching close to 30%, which is much higher than biomass production (typically less than 1%). Since fulfilling societal energy and commodities needs will be no longer a distant, out-of-sight activity but an activity close to one's household, distinguished by a highly decentralized character and spanning across densely populated urban areas, societal acceptance will dominate environmental benefits. Existing paradigms of nature as a resource to be exploited or of humans as passive consumers of natural resources are inadequate. For a full appreciation of the capacities and complexities of incorporating SUNRISE technologies in an existing ecosystem, their impact on human dignity will be evaluated and key stakeholders from society will be involved from the start in making strategic choices. Their input in filling in the innovation pipelines will optimize the overall societal and environmental impact by increasing the connection to the general public interests. A pipeline of plug-in technologies allows the connection to the existing technological infrastructure and strengthen its further development, defined by the economic efficiency requirements from the market and people's desires. The limited redundancy will help to find the best technological solutions by offering choices on the supply side of the circular economy, also to avoid potential environmental pitfalls and thus contribute to reducing costs and facilitating societal acceptance of the technology.

5.2 Overview of the priority research directions

The following sections provide short overviews of the pipeline of technologies for the main technological challenges to be resolved in Figure 2.

5.2.1 Combine water electrolysis with CO₂ capture for the fully integrated value chain

Figure 4. The innovation pipelines for the 1st PRD, conventional electrolysis with CO₂ conversion, worked out for the block arrows in Figure 2 with the technology routes from the SUNRISE roadmap.

The innovation pipeline for combining water electrolysis with CO₂ capture over the source to product value chain is shown in Figure 4. The pipeline encompasses a cluster of four IA's with KPIs (magenta) concentrating on technologies for the production of chemicals and (jet) fuels with adequate stability, efficiency and selectivity (red), for capturing CO₂ (silver) from concentrated sources at a price of 50€/ton or from the air at a price of 300€/ton. The IA cluster feeds into plant scale innovation by connecting to other initiatives in Europe for scaling up and with synergy for improving economic efficiency, for the commercial manufacturing of chemicals and (jet) fuel with direct air capture at a price of 100€/ton CO₂.

5.2.2 Does integration of steps (PV+electrolysis vs PEC vs molecular vs biological) give better processes in terms of efficiency, selectivity/purity, concentration over the value chain?

The innovation trajectories for the block arrows in Figure 2 with a grid of RIA's and IA's and KPIs (magenta) from the SUNRISE roadmap for resolving if integration of steps (PV+electrolysis vs PEC vs molecular vs biological) gives better processes in terms of efficiency, selectivity/purity, concentration over the value chain are shown in Figure 5. This PRD is very research intensive and photo(electro)chemically oriented, and starting TRLs are generally low. This is in line with international developments in the field (mainly from the US) where research attention is shifting from separate PV with catalysis to direct conversion. For hydrogen PEC (blue), the current state of the art is 50% photon to hydrogen yield (20% STH) due to detrimental recombination losses and

Figure 5. The innovation pipelines for the 2nd PRD, integration, worked out for the block arrows in Figure x with the technology routes from the SUNRISE roadmap.

with poor materials efficiency. The target is to improve this with bottom-up systems engineering of responsive matrices and PEC with biomimetic catalysts to 70% photon to product yield (30% STH, 16 mA/cm² tandem current), beyond the adiabatic limit, with good materials efficiency, followed by a distributed demonstration in relevant operating environments, with reducing the water requirement. This is followed by an IA step for systems integration with hydrogen collection and storage. For the production of ammonia (green) further integration with PEC for one order of magnitude, and microorganisms with ATP independent nitrogen fixation enzymes for integration in hydroponic production value chains is investigated with three parallel RIA lines, followed by demonstrations in relevant operation environments of the best outcomes for integration of membrane based catalysts in electrolyzers, PEC with >10% solar to NH₃ efficiency, and system integration of NH₃ and NH₄⁺ collection with microorganisms. A very important challenge is the development of DAC, which will start with a concentrated, all-out intensive effort of 10 RIAs running into 3 demonstrators for direct oxygen-tolerant conversion of CO₂ absorbed from the atmosphere. The next step is an IA to forge the manufacturing tools to make a thermochemical or PEC route for direct conversion of CO₂ commercially available. For the direct production chemicals and fuels 5 RIAs will provide coupling of PEC with direct air capture and demonstration of a commercial photo(electro)chemical device, while on the biology side demo plants for TRL4 chemical products (10 ton/yr) and proof-of-concept (POC) products (t/yr) will be scaled up to the 100 kt/y level for the production of chemicals and fuels at a competitive price.

5.2.3 How do we get all the hydrogen to decarbonize

The single prioritizing criterion across the entire S&T framework is demonstration of the value chain from source to product. To provide sufficient hydrogen to decarbonize, three innovation routes from Figure 2 are grouped under this innovation pipeline, sustainable hydrogen production with PV+electrolysis (blue), sustainable hydrogen production with microorganisms (blue), and Haber-Bosch with solar hydrogen (green) in Figure 6. For the PV+electrolysis, two demonstration projects are foreseen, to integrate with other renewables, mainly wind, and to use low exergy rest energy, from renewable waste heat, or from the recovery of exergy from the solar photons at the PV stage before thermalization takes place. The KPI (magenta) is improvement of the value chain (and reduction of CAPEX) by integration with wind and using renewable residual heat. This is followed by a broad effort to move away from the current practice of expensive Ir and Pt catalysts, where control over residual heat provides a route to solid oxide electrolysis at elevated temperatures to improve efficiencies. At this stage a PEC booster is added to connect to the PEC development in the pipeline focusing on the question if decentralized is preferred over centralized conversion. The KPI at the end of this stage is an effective yield of 90 ton H₂/ha.yr at a cost price of 4€/kg H₂ operating at the 20 MW scale. Further upscaling is foreseen with a pillar 3 equity-financed plant scale demonstration effort for upscaling to the 1000 ha/400 MW scale at a cost price of 3€/kg of concentrated H₂.

Figure 6. The innovation pipelines for the 3rd PRD, (bio)hydrogen, worked out for the block arrows in Figure 2 with the technology routes from the SUNRISE roadmap.

Also for the microorganisms the value chain in principle exists, with CAPEX and other limitations. An RIA stage focusing on novel protocols and cultivation strategies to increase efficiency (KPI) is foreseen. The lessons learned from this stage will also serve the innovation pipeline aiming for decentralized applications, as the technology is naturally suitable for domestic application. This is followed by demonstration of the bottom-up systems integration with separation and collection of hydrogen. Following positive evaluation and a go/no go decision, scale up will proceed with an IA focusing on a broad effort for improved enzyme catalysis with oxygen tolerant hydrogenase and improved light harvesting in biohybrid systems that incorporate human made light harvesters such as quantum dots or supramolecular structures. At the end of this stage such advanced biological and biohybrid systems should be commercially available (KPI). Since the single prioritizing criterion is demonstration of the source to product value chain, we have added with Haber-Bosch a route where a very mature existing, energy-intensive value chain needs decarbonization by running it from an alternative energy source and hydrogen is an important early intermediate. Following the demonstration of integration of wind and low exergy energy, an IA is started in Haber-Bosch with solar hydrogen aiming for novel catalysis and plasma-assisted processes for low temperature and low pressure. In parallel, an RIA and demonstration trajectory is planned for electrochemical and plasma-assisted processes to speed up catalysis by two orders of magnitude. This is followed by a pillar 3 upscaling that feeds into a global societal deliverable, which is 80% decoupling of economic growth from the use of natural resources.

5.3 Overview of the SUNRISE technologies

The roadmap provides four technological routes for innovation, for hydrogen, ammonia, carbon capture and production of fuel and chemicals, with key performance indicators for their development over 10 years.

5.3.1 Sustainable hydrogen production

The need:

Decarbonisation across sectors presents the potential demand for generating approximately 2,250 TWh of hydrogen in Europe in 2050, representing roughly a quarter of the EU's total energy demand. This amount would fuel about 42 million large cars, 1.7 million trucks, approximately a quarter of a million buses, and more than 5,500 trains. It would heat more than the equivalent of 52 million households (about 465 TWh) and provide as much as 10% of building power demand. In industry, approximately 160 TWh of hydrogen would produce high-grade heat and another 140 TWh would replace coal in steelmaking processes in the form of direct reduced iron (DRI). 120 TWh of hydrogen combined with captured carbon or carbon from biomass would also produce synthetic feedstock for 40 Mt of chemicals in 2050. Achieving this vision puts the EU on a path to reducing about 560 Mt of CO₂ emissions by 2050 – as much as half of the required abatement needed to achieve the 2-degree scenario. The EU needs to reduce its CO₂ emissions from 3,500 Mt today to 770 Mt in 2050. Deploying available technologies and existing energy and climate-related commitments from European countries would close approximately 60% of the gap (approximately 1,700 Mt in the Reference Technology Scenario). The use of hydrogen in end sectors could help reduce half of the remaining 1,100 Mt and achieve the 2-degree scenario. In addition, it could enable deep decarbonization of the power sector and hence indirectly reduce carbon emissions [reference: Hydrogen Roadmap Europe - A sustainable Pathway for the European Energy Transition, 2019].

The technologies:

Electrochemical conversion

The electrochemical conversion of water produces oxygen and molecular hydrogen, a key enabler in our vision. By using renewable electricity sources, hydrogen production becomes a sustainable source of fuel and chemical building blocks. The challenge, preventing the world from using this technology today, is to scale up the production to reach the amounts needed to replace fossil-based hydrogen and also to compete with the costs of hydrogen produced from natural gas (about 1€/kg vs. 5-7 €/kg for green hydrogen). It is necessary to find materials that can make this technology environmentally sustainable and economically feasible. We aim to tackle this challenge by inspiring the development of new, sustainable and non-toxic materials for large-scale deployment of electrolysis driven by power from renewable sources.

Direct conversion via photo(electro)chemical systems

Photoelectrochemical cells are single devices that directly split water into hydrogen and oxygen, using energy provided by sunlight. A variety of architectures combine light-harvesting materials and catalysts for the hydrogen and the oxygen evolving reactions. The integration of all components into a single device can lower the total system cost compared to electrochemical conversion, and

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provide greater flexibility in the design. Compact, integrated devices, which are independent of the electrical grid, allow for a decentralized production and important savings in transportation costs (transport and compression significantly add up to actual hydrogen production costs, leading to hydrogen prices at the fuel station of around 10 €/kg). Photo(electro)chemical systems will be fully autonomous, only depending on abundantly available sunlight, thus providing suitable solutions for on-demand, on-site production.

Devices for photo(electro)chemical hydrogen production are still at the laboratory stage, where some have reached solar-to-hydrogen conversion efficiencies of up to 20%. Ongoing research efforts are searching for ultimate combinations of light absorbing and catalytic materials, finding ways of making these materials stable under highly demanding photochemical conditions, and finding routes to the scaling up of integrated devices to pilot scale.

5.3.2 Sustainable ammonia production

The need:

Ammonia synthesis via the Haber-Bosch process ($\text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{NH}_3$) uses about 1% of all energy in the world with a comparable share of CO_2 emissions (since the H_2 comes from fossil sources), the latter of which will be substantially reduced using 'green' hydrogen. In addition, local fertiliser production will help alleviate issues related to ammonia transport and storage and allow the continuous application of fertilisers during the growing season, solving thereby the considerable environmental problems associated with fertiliser run-off.

This is required as an internal flexibility option to create a negative feedback when excessive renewable energy is available. Ammonia could be used as a fertiliser in Europe or as an energy transport vector with vanishing CO_2 footprint.

The technologies:

Electrochemical conversion

A similar possibility exists to convert nitrogen (N_2) from the atmosphere into ammonia (NH_3) that can be accomplished via electrochemistry, by-passing the need for prior hydrogen production. This is still in an early stage, with low efficiencies in the few demonstrated examples. Non-thermal plasma-assisted synthesis is an alternative for chemical conversions using electrical power.

Major ongoing scientific developments are making new, highly effective catalysts achievable. These include theoretical methods with predictive power, advanced catalyst synthesis with atom-scale precision, and operando characterization methods. These approaches can be integrated and combined with new machine learning methodology and artificial intelligence (AI) to enable radically accelerated catalyst and chemical process discovery.

Direct conversion via photo(electro)chemical systems

Similar to direct solar hydrogen production, photoelectrochemical systems have the potential to allow for decentralized ammonia production at lower cost compared to other techniques. Although photoelectrochemical nitrogen fixation is still at its very infancy, rapid progress can be expected as a result of the current expansion of this research field. The discovery of catalysts for nitrogen

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fixation will push the development of devices that can reach 10% solar-to-ammonia efficiency in integrated collections of aqueous ammonia.

5.3.3 Sustainable carbon capture

The need:

Many policy and industrial drivers exist to accelerate the deployment of carbon capture technologies.

The technology:

Direct air capture and conversion:

One topic will be directly impacted by SUNRISE ideas and is thus addressed in more details: the research towards combined processes of capture and activation of CO₂ for chemical conversion. At present, different types of carbon capture technologies are being developed that are based on the extraction of CO₂ from point sources. The most mature technologies consist of separating and concentrating CO₂ by chemical or physical absorption (*e.g.* utilizing amine solvent) or by adsorption (using a solid sorbent or membranes). Besides, the atmosphere is a potentially huge (teraton scale) CO₂ reservoir for decentralized systems, but with a concentration of only about 400 ppm. This will require highly efficient separation from oxygen and nitrogen, especially for electrochemical and photo(electro)chemical methods.

5.3.4 Sustainable production of commodity chemicals and (jet) fuels

The need:

The European chemical industry is globally leading, is one of the largest industrial greenhouse gas emitters accounting for the use of more than 10% of all fossil resources in Europe, and is completely dependent on fossil-based raw materials and energy carriers. The fossil fuel market is by far the largest market. European fossil fuel imports are 180 billion €/yr, and 225 billion €/yr downstream processes. In addition, the infrastructure replacement market is 150 billion €/yr globally.

The technologies:

Electrochemical conversion

Decreasing the CO₂ net emissions via electrochemical processes exploiting renewable electricity and water to produce synthetic fuels and valuable carbon-based chemicals is a promising pathway. Currently operating processes are at a TRL of 4-6 with more than 75% efficiency. Although the technologies are at an industrial relevant stage already, the stability of the catalysts is poor and needs further improvement against poisoning and increase in stability forwards fluctuating operation conditions.

Direct conversion via photo(electro)chemical systems

Similar to direct solar hydrogen production, photo(electro)chemical systems have the potential to allow for a decentralized CO₂ valorisation at lower costs compared to PV-driven electrolysis. Photo(electro)chemical cells for CO₂ valorisation into CO or syngas are at a similar stage of development as those for H₂ production, with key drivers being discovery of CO₂ reducing catalysts that can be combined with light-absorbing materials, improvement of stability, designing active components solely based on earth-abundant elements, and collection of gases. An important target is to couple direct air capture (DAC) technologies with commercial PEC devices with 10% solar-to-syngas efficiency.

Direct conversion via biological and biohybrid systems

We recommend the domestication of a broad range of microorganisms that use solar energy for the sustainable biocatalytic production of diverse fuels and feedstock for the chemical industry. Until now, such cell factories live from a supply of biomass with high energy content. Although this can be made sustainable on a small scale, it is not scalable to produce the enormous quantities of fuels and chemicals. We therefore recommend the rational redesign of photosynthetic organisms by engineering them to have new abilities for converting atmospheric CO₂ into products with high at least 70% light to product yield, and design biohybrid systems that feed solar electricity, hydrogen, or carbon based feedstock into non-photosynthetic organisms for further downstream conversion with high yield, and using ambient CO₂ as the only carbon source. The first photosynthetic designer organisms are already coming out of scientific laboratories for testing in the field, but much improvement is still needed. A genuine rational engineering theory for smooth light conversion into rapidly growing product supplies is highly desired, synthetic biology requires further development, and the cost of bioreactors needs to be reduced while enhancing their performance. With the synergistic approach of a large-scale research program it will be possible to establish the first demonstrators for butanol or ethylene fuel at the kton scale and for selected chemicals such as lactic acid on the 10 kton scale by 2025. By 2030 production will be at industrial scale with plants producing 100 kton per year at a competitive price. This is estimated at replacing up to 10% per year of the existing refinery infrastructure, which is currently valued at €1700 billion worldwide.

5.4 Implementation with a synergistic framework of calls

SUNRISE technology	Current TRL	TRL target 2030	Companies involved	Private investments (estimate)	Public investments (estimate)	Comments
1. Sustainable hydrogen production						
1a. PV-driven electrolysis of water	4-6	9	Siemens (DE) Nel (NO) ITM (UK) Hydrogenics (US, BE) Areva H2Gen (FR)	40% C FI p.m.	30% EU 30% MS	IA Demo 2
1b. Photoelectrochemical devices	2-4	5-8	Engie (FR) Siemens (DE) SABIC (NL)	20% IA	100% RIA (MS) 80%IA (MS) 100% DD	RIA IA Distributed demo
1c. Transparent baggie systems (microorganisms and photocatalytic systems)	3-4	6-8	Mitsubishi (J) Hypersolar (US) H2WIN (BE)	40% IA	100% RIA+D 60% IA	RIA lab demo (g/ng)IA
2. Sustainable ammonia production						
2a. Low-emission Haber-Bosch	5-6	9	Yara (NO) Casale (CH) Thyssenkrupp (DE) Haldor Topsøes (DK) Siemens (DE)	40	30EU 30MS	IA demo
2b. Electrochemical and plasma-assisted ammonia synthesis	1-2	4-5	n.a.		100 RIA (MS) 100 DP (MS)	2 RIA 1 Demo project
2c. Photoelectrochemical devices	1-2	4-5	n.a.		100 RIA (MS) 100 DP	2 RIA 1 Demoproject
2d. Microorganisms for direct fertilizer production	1-2	4-6	H2WIN (BE)		100 RIA (MS) 100 DP	2 RIA 1 Demoproject
3. Sustainable carbon capture						
3a. CO ₂ capture from concentrated sources (concentrate on local value creation) co-adaptation of capture and catalytic conversion into long term deposits	6-7	9	ENGIE (F) (orchestrate) Fluor (US) Mitsubishi (J) Siemens (DE) Aker solutions (NO) Shell (NL) Solvay (BE) AirLiquide (US) MTR (US) RWE (DE) BASF (DE) LINDE Engineering (DE)	30% IA cluster Pipeline will feed into larger DEMOs	70% cluster	IA Demo upscaling link to 4.1 and 4.2 TEAM up with Separate Big 300 ME demo in pillar 3
3b. Direct CO ₂ Capture from the atmosphere	6	8-9	Climeworks (CH) Antecy (NL) Global Thermostat (US) Carbon Engineering (Canada) Ineratec (DE) Carbyon (NL)	30% IA cluster Pipeline will feed into ongoing large demo	70% IA cluster	IA including RIA and Demo (Don't forget low exergy energy) link to 4.1 and 4.2 Don't forget negative emission (1MW scale)
3c. Direct Atmospheric CO ₂ Capture & Conversion including PEC	1-2	5-7	n.a.	40 IA	100 (MS) 30 IA 30 MS IA	10 RIA 3 Demoproject g/ng IA (don't forget low exergy energy)
4. Sustainable production of commodity chemicals and (jet) fuels						

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<i>4a-1. Electrochemical water splitting and thermocatalytic conversion of CO₂</i>	6	9	Airline Global Alliance Powerfuels Aireg (DE) Sunfire (DE) Ineratec (DE)	30%	70%	2 IA clusters FT and methanol) feeding into Demo plant
<i>4a-2. Direct electroreduction of CO₂</i>	3	6	Velocys (US) BASF (DE) Casale (CH)		100 (MS)	4-5 RIA feeding into 2 demo
<i>4b. Direct solar-thermochemical conversion of water and CO₂</i>	4-5	6	Total (FR) Synhelion (CH) Toyota (J, BE) Abengoa (ES) Brightsource (Isr) Helpe (GR)	40 IA	100 (MS) RIA 30 EU IA 30 MS IA	RIA demo g/ng IA upscaler demo plant
<i>4c. Biocatalytic production of carbon-based solar fuels and chemicals</i>	1-6	4-9	Photanol (NL) Ecoduna (AU) Synthetic Genomics (US) Euglena (J) Total (FR) Neste (FI) H2WIN (BE)	40 IA	100 RIA (MS) 100 RIA (MS) 30 EU (IA) 30 MS(IA)	8 RIA and 3 demo and 1 small IA Demo plant 100 kt/yr

This list of calls corresponds to a full scenario for a large-scale research initiative under HE, equivalent to a full Flagship under H2020.

Notes from within the consortium:

- In this table, every IA initiative stands for *ca.* 100 M€ investment, RIA initiatives are typically 5 M€ per contract, and the scale of demonstration projects is up to 10 M€.
- In IA calls the costs of private partners are not fully reimbursed (only up to 70%) which means that actual corporate costs are higher. This has to be taken into account when making the split between private and public investments
- A distinction is made between ‘small demonstrators’ (*i.e.* working devices in operating conditions) in demonstration projects and ‘full demonstrators’ (*i.e.* large pilot plants) in IA’s, the latter being far more important for companies.
- Central management of the projects will need to be steered by a CSA: Assuming a total project portfolio of 1 b€, 1% (10 M€) is assumed to be sufficient to run the CSA component at a level of 1 M€/year.
- Education and governance, including the programming and monitoring of progress, are organised in the central CSA.
- Infrastructure costs can be charged to projects.
- For specification and testing of technology bids will be called for from centers that will be qualified to perform this work. Budget: 10 M€ in total for 1-3 centers associated with either PV centers or hydrogen valleys, depending on the costs.
- Quantitative sustainability analysis is mandatory for every project with go/no go decisions from the QIA team and program board
- Dissemination is in every project, in addition there is global dissemination at the partnership level with the management
- Risk mitigation is by running multiple technologies in parallel, providing optimal cross-fertilization for maximum synergy benefits and establishing an open innovation environment with respect to founding and transferring IP. For example, in a power-to-ethanol demonstrator plant (IA) it is possible to exchange different electrolyzers. Another example is to aim for ‘distributed demos’, e.g. plants distributed over countries with low/high solar irradiation intensity.

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- A mid-term review will be performed by an independent group of experts and QIA processes will be implemented to discuss the project results regularly (see also governance deliverable 4.1 that contains the procedures).
- The companies listed in the table were mentioned during the discussions at the consortium meeting on February 7, 2020. However, they do not necessarily represent a complete overview.
- Since a significant part of the work is performed on high TRL, we expect to get access to another billion in pillar 3, and in addition the innovation fund related to public money coming from the carbon tax 2020-2030. However, it must be noted that SUNRISE / SUNERGY will only control specific technology developments, such as PEC, and the rest we feed into:
 - For regional SUNRISE valleys, it is proposed that they could line up with hydrogen valleys. Pillar 3 could be sourced for the demonstrators when they end successfully. This will be equity or bond financed, *i.e.* not in our budget. In this case, central management will move out as they will operate on their own, central management will only monitor
 - CO₂ capture is already being done at large-scale. Best is to team up with ongoing efforts and focus on e.g. capture with integrated conversion.
 - Negative emissions are not covered in the Sunrise roadmap and in the blueprint.
- Table 4a: New fuel components will require certification for use in jet fuels, there are standard specifications in place for synthetic jet fuel components. The certification process takes many years and costs several M€.
- Table 4b: Several demonstrations are already out in the field. However, since these are relatively small-scale, we will aim for “upscaler demonstration plants”.

APPENDIX

In the following tables we list all organizations that have been identified during the mapping of the required competencies and identification of key partners (see section 3.1 above). The organizations have been selected based on: 1. Supporting organizations that have specifically expressed their interest and support for SUNRISE or Energy-X; 2. Member organizations of EERA, relevant for the area; 3. after a consultation with the supporters on a draft of the blueprint, the received feedback was used to finalize the coverage of expertises and parties. For detailed information on the key competences of selected organizations, see the descriptions in Section 3. Most universities and research institutions have several key competencies in the area as of 2020, and with the strong interest in the research area of SUNRISE, the number is growing rapidly.

Table 1: *Overview of selected European research organisations and companies interested to contribute to SUNRISE roadmap task group 1: Sustainable hydrogen*

Organization name	Country	Organization type
University of Copenhagen	DK	University
Technical University Graz	AT	University
Technical University Berlin	DE	University
Technical University of Munich	DE	University
European Atlas of Universities in Energy Research & Education, EUA-EPUE	BE	University network
Psi-K	CH	Academic network
INSTM	IT	University network
PTChem	PO	Academic society
Societa Chimica Italiana, SCI	IT	Academic society
Société Chimique de France	FR	Academic society
F.R.S.-FNRS	BE	Academic network
Polish National Science Centre (NCN)	PO	Academic network
Czech Academy of Science	CZ	Academic network
Palacký University Olomouc - Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials	CZ	University
Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne	CH	University
University of Warsaw	PO	University
KU Leuven	BE	University
University of Milano-Bicocca	IT	University
Queen's University Belfast	UK	University
Uppsala University	SE	University
Freie Universität Berlin	DE	University
Imperial College	UK	University
Danish Technical University	DK	University
Universität Zurich	CH	University
University of Stockholm	SE	University
University of Antwerp	BE	University
National University of Ireland Galway	IR	University
University of Padova	IT	University
University Bari Aldo Moro	IT	University
University of Turku	FI	University
Leibniz Institute for Catalysis	DE	University
University of Tartu, Institute of Physics	EE	University
Leiden University	NL	University
University of Camerino	IT	University
TU Dresden	DE	University
University Bielefeld	DE	University
Ruhr-University Bochum	DE	University
University of Seville	ES	University
Lund University	SE	University
Mersin University	TR	University
Bogazici University	TR	University
University of Twente	NL	University

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University of Freiburg	DE	University
University of Kiel	DE	University
University of York	UK	University
Technical University of Delft	NL	University
University of Cambridge	UK	University
Univ. Rey Juan Carlos	ES	University
University of Oxford	UK	University
University of Amsterdam	NL	University
Johannes Kepler University Linz	AT	University
Warsaw University of Life Sciences	PO	University
University of Umea	SE	University
University of Lorraine	FR	University
University of Crete, Chemistry Department	GR	University
University of Limerick	IRL	University
University of Bologna	IT	University
University of Ferrara	IT	University
National University of Ireland Galway (NUIG)	IRL	University
Tarsus University	TR	University
Uni. Oldenburg	DE	University
IASS Potsdam	DE	University
UK catalysis hub	UK	University network
UK Solar Fuels Network	UK	University network
NERA	NL	University network
LERU	BE	University network
Swedish Consortium for Artificial Photosynthesis	SE	University network
Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion	DE	Institute
CIEMAT	ES	Institute
CNRS	FR	Institute
CERIC-ERIC Trieste	IT	Institute
DLR	DE	Institute
TNO	NL	Institute
ENEA	IT	Institute
IFP Energies Nouvelles, IFPEN	FR	Institute
Hellenic Mediterranean University	GR	Institute
IBPC	ES	Institute
VTT Finland	FI	Institute
CEA	FR	Institute
J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry	CZ	Institute
College de France	FR	Institute
Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht	DE	Institute
Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH	DE	Institute
Fondazione Bruno Kessler	IT	Institute
German Aerospace Center	DE	Institute
Paul - Scherrer Institute	DE	Institute
Fraunhofer Gesellschaft	DE	Institute
Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin	DE	Institute
Italian National Research Council (CNR)	IT	Institute
SPF_Inst. Fuer Solar Technik (HRS Rapperswil)	CH	Institute
KTH	SE	Institute
ICIQ	ES	Institute
AIT - Austrian Institute of Technology	AT	Institute
EMPA	CH	Institute

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DIFFER	NL	Institute
Biological Research Center_BRC, Laboratory of Photosynthetic Membranes	HU	Institute
IREC	ES	Institute
Tecnalia	ES	Institute
Ricerca Sistema Energetico	IT	Institute
UKERC	UK	Institute
BAS	BG	Institute
CNH2	ES	Institute
IEN	PO	Institute
IK4	ES	Institute
IMPPAN	PO	Institute
MINES Paris-Tech	FR	Institute
NTNU	NO	Institute
TUBITAK	TR	Institute
Helmholtz centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Leipzig	DE	Institute
Bauhaus Luftfahrt	DE	Institute
Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, ACIB	AT	Institute
Interuniversity Microelectronics centre, IMEC	BE	Institute
Johnson-Matthey	UK	Company
Evonik	DE	Company
Siemens	DE	Company
Engie	FR	Company
3M	ES	Company
Acciona Energy	PT	Company
EDP Energia	ES	Company
ENAGAS	ES	Company
H2WIN	BE	Company
Repsol	ES	Company
Schaeffler	DE	Company
ST1 Oy	FI	Company
Total S.A.	FR	Company
Toyota Motor Europe	BE	Company
Uniper	DE	Company
Shell	NL	Company
Arcelor Mittal	LU	Company
Copenhagen airports	DK	Company
Avantium	NL	Company
PCM	UK	Company
Carbon Recyclin International, CRI	IS	Company
Canal de Isabel II	ES	Company
CEGASA	ES	Company
Cyano Biotech	DE	Company
Esy-labs	DE	Company
Everest Coatings	NL	Company
Dr Laure Plasmatechnologie	DE	Company
Fortum	FI	Company
Hydron Energy	NL	Company
NOVAMONT	IT	Company
PEPPERPRINT	DE	Company
Photanol	NL	Company
Plasmatechnologie GmbH	DE	Company
PowerCell	SE	Company
Proheat – Heat Traces	ES	Company
PVH_Energy Storage	ES	Company
SCM Amsterdam	NL	Company

Sulapac	FI	Company
InCatT	NL	Company
EuChemS - European Chemical Society	BE	Society
ANCRE	FR	Network organization
EMIRI	BE	Network organization
Association of Chemical Industry of the Czech Republic	CZ	Network organization
GDR Solar Fuels French Network	FR	Network organization
Innovation Quarter	NL	Network organization
MATERPLAT	ES	Network organization
Swedish Energy Agency	SE	Network organization
Swedish Research Council	SE	Network organization
DECHEMA	DE	Network organisation
Fonden Teknologirådet	DK	Funding agency
European Algae Biomass Association, EABA		Association
Hydrogen Sweden	SE	Public Private Partnership
Mariestad	SE	Municipality
Polish Ministry of Science and Education	PO	Ministry
Regional Ministry of E&R in comunidad de Madrid	ES	Municipality

Table 2: *Overview of selected European research organisations and companies interested to contribute to SUNRISE roadmap task group 2: Sustainable ammonia*

Organization name	Country	Organization type
University Perugia	IT	University
University of Freiburg	DE	University
Universität Rostock for Biowissenschaften	DE	University
University Pau and Pays de l'Adour	FR	University
University of Turku	FI	University
Lund University	SE	University
Ege University (Bioengineering)	TR	University
Chalmers University of Technology	SE	University
TU München	DE	University
University of York	UK	University
University of Oxford	UK	University
European Atlas of Universities in Energy Research & Education, EUA-EPUE	BE	University network
Psi-K	CH	Academic network
INSTM	IT	University network
PTChem	PO	Academic society
Societa Chimica Italiana, SCI	IT	Academic society
Société Chimique de France	FR	Academic society
F.R.S.-FNRS	BE	Academic network
Polish National Science Centre (NCN)	PO	Academic network
Czech Academy of Science	CZ	Academic network
Uppsala University	SE	University
University of Stockholm	SE	University
Imperial College	UK	University
University of Warsaw	PO	University
Ruhr-University Bochum	DE	University
Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan	PO	University
University of Iceland	IS	University
University Roma 3_Campus bio-medico	IT	University
University of Glasgow	UK	University
Technical University of Denmark	DK	University
Universität Hamburg	DE	University
University of Cambridge	UK	University
University of Nantes	FR	University
UK catalysis hub	UK	University network
NERA	NL	University network
LERU	BE	University network
University of Lorraine	FR	University
University of East Anglia	UK	University
University of Stuttgart	DE	University
University of Kiel - Botanical Institute and Garden	DE	University
University of Sheffield	UK	University
University of Limerick	IRL	University
National University of Ireland Galway	IRL	University
University of Bologna	IT	University
University of Ferrara	IT	University
University of Umea	SE	University
UKERC	UK	Institute
CIEMAT	ES	Institute
CNRS	FR	Institute
CERIC-ERIC_Trieste	IT	Institute
DLR	DE	Institute
AIT - Austrian Institute of Technology	AT	Institute

TNO	NL	Institute
ENEA	IT	Institute
IFP Energies Nouvelles, IFPEN	FR	Institute
IBPC	ES	Institute
SCK-CEN	BE	Institute
Fonden Teknologirådet	DK	Funding agency
VTT Finland	FI	Institute
Cyano Biotech	DE	Institute
Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH	DE	Institute
Fundacion IMDEA Energia	ES	Institute
Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion	DE	Institute
Lyon Sustainable Development Chair	FR	Institute
Biological Research Center_BRC, Institute of Plant Biology	HU	Institute
EMPA	CH	Institute
J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry	CZ	Institute
IREC	ES	Institute
Tecnia	ES	Institute
ICIQ	ES	Institute
Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, ACIB	AT	Institute
3M	ES	Company
Acciona Energy	PT	Company
EDP Energia	ES	Company
H2WIN	BE	Company
ST1 Oy	FI	Company
Avantium	NL	Company
Carbon Recycling International, CRI	IS	Company
Cyano Biotech	DE	Company
Esy-labs	DE	Company
Dr Laure Plasmatechnologie	DE	Company
NOVAMONT	IT	Company
Engie	FR	Company
PEPPERPRINT	DE	Company
Photanol	NL	Company
Plasmatechnologie GmbH	DE	Company
SCM Amsterdam	NL	Company
Sulapac	FI	Company
Casale	CH	Company
Clariant	CH	Company
Haldor Topsoe	DK	Company
Stamicarbon	NL	Company
Yara	NO	Company
MATERPLAT	ES	Network organization
ANCRE	FR	Network organization
Association of Chemical Industry of the Czech Republic	CZ	Network organization
GDR Solar Fuels French Network	FR	Network organization
Innovation Quarter	NL	Network organization
Swedish Energy Agency	SE	Network organization
EuChemS - European Chemical Society	BE	Society
DECHEMA	DE	Network organisation
European Algae Biomass Association, EABA		Association
Polish Ministry of Science and Education	PO	Ministry

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Regional Ministry of E&R in comunidad de Madrid	ES	Municipality
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Table 3: *Overview of selected European research organisations and companies interested to contribute to SUNRISE roadmap task group 3: Sustainable carbon capture*

Organization name	Country	Organization type
Valladoid University Spain	ES	University
University of Bern	CH	University
Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne	CH	University
Uni Stuttgart_Institute of Chemical Technology	DE	University
Technical University of Delft	NL	University
Technical University of Denmark	DK	University
University of Szeged	HU	University
University of Zaragoza	ES	University
National University of Ireland Galway (NUIG)	IRL	University
Leiden University	NL	University
Johannes Kepler University Linz	AT	University
University of Ferrara	IT	University
University of Gothenburg	SE	University
JGU Mainz	DE	University
Bogazici University	TR	University
Dept. of Atomic Physics_BME	HU	University
Tampere University	FI	University
University of Nova Gorica	SI	University
Hasselt University	BE	University
Technische Universitat Kaiserslautern	DE	University
University of Milano-Bicocca	IT	University
Warsaw University of Life Sciences	PO	University
Lund University	SE	University
University of Strasbourg	FR	University
Centrale Lille University	FR	University
Queen's University Belfast	UK	University
University of Warsaw	PO	University
University of Paris Diderot	FR	University
University of Alicante	ES	University
University of Messina	IT	University
University of Duisburg-Essen	DE	University
Cardiff University	UK	University
Aachen University	DE	University
Hochschule Osnabrück	ES	University
Technical University of Denmark	DK	University
University of Utrecht	NL	University
Ghent University	BE	University
Karlsruhe Institute of Catalysis	DE	University
Ruhr-University Bochum	DE	University
Humboldt University	DE	University
University of Milano	IT	University
Wageningen University	NL	University
University of Manchester	UK	University
University of Firenze/UNIFI	IT	University
Politecnico di Milano	IT	University
University of Antwerp	BE	University
Maria Curie-Sklodowska University_UMCS_Gruszecki	PO	University
European Atlas of Universities in Energy Research & Education, EUA-EPUE	BE	University network
Psi-K	CH	Academic network
UK catalysis hub	UK	University network
NERA	NL	University network

LERU	BE	University network
INSTM	IT	University network
PTChem	PO	Academic society
Societa Chimica Italiana, SCI	IT	Academic society
Société Chimique de France	FR	Academic society
F.R.S.-FNRS	BE	Academic network
Polish National Science Centre (NCN)	PO	Academic network
European Materials Research Society, EMRS		Academic network
Leibniz Institute for Catalysis	DE	Institute
CIEMAT	ES	Institute
CNRS	FR	Institute
CERIC-ERIC_Trieste	IT	Institute
DLR	DE	Institute
TNO	NL	Institute
AIT - Austrian Institute of Technology	AT	Institute
ENEA	IT	Institute
IFP Energies Nouvelles, IFPEN	FR	Institute
Fundacion IMDEA Energia	ES	Institute
Institute of Microstructure technology	DE	Institute
Bauhaus Luftfahrt	DE	Institute
UKERC	UK	Institute
Fraunhofer Gesellschaft	DE	Institute
Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH	DE	Institute
Leibniz Institute for Catalysis	DE	Institute
Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, ACIB	AT	Institute
INL_Lyon Institute of Nanotechnology UMR-CNRS	FR	Institute
Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society	DE	Institute
CEA	FR	Institute
Institute of Physics of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine	UA	Institute
ICIQ	ES	Institute
Weizmann Institute of Science and Bar-Ilan University	IL	Institute
NPK ERHVERV	DK	Institute
National Institute of Chemistry	SI	Institute
Tecnalia	ES	Institute
Eindhoven University of Technology	NL	Institute
Institutt for energiteknikk (IFE)	NO	Institute
J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry	CZ	Institute
CENER	ES	Institute
Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht	DE	Institute
ITQ Institute of Chemical Technology (CSIC-UPV)	IT	Institute
NTNU	NO	Institute
ETH Zurich	CH	Institute
SINTEF Energy	NO	Institute
CSIC-INCAR	ES	Institute
3M	ES	Company
Acciona Energy	PT	Company
EDP Energia	ES	Company
ENAGAS	ES	Company
H2WIN	BE	Company
Repsol	ES	Company
ST1 Oy	FI	Company

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Total S.A.	FR	Company
Toyota Motor Europe	BE	Company
Uniper	DE	Company
Shell	NL	Company
Arcelor Mittal	LU	Company
Copenhagen airports	DK	Company
Esy-labs	DE	Company
Everest Coatings	NL	Company
Dr Laure Plasmatechnologie	DE	Company
Hydron Energy	NL	Company
NOVAMONT	IT	Company
PEPperPRINT	DE	Company
Plasmatechnologie GmbH	DE	Company
Proheat – Heat Traces	ES	Company
SCM Amsterdam	NL	Company
HUNOSA	ES	Company
Siemens	DE	Company
Johnson Matthey	UK	Company
Engie	FR	Company
LafargeHolcim	FR	Company
Lhoist	BE	Company
Solvay S.A.	BE	Company
Skytree	NL	Company
Carbyon	NL	Company
C&CS catalysts and chemical specialties	DE	Company
Petrogal SA	PT	Company
Arkema France	FR	Company
Stamicarbon	NL	Company
Atmostat - Alcen	FR	Company
GreenWin	BE	Company
Ingenza	UK	Company
Liquid Wind	SE	Company
PlasmaAir AG	DE	Company
Plasmatreat GmbH	DE	Company
Climeworks	CH	Company
Marion Technologies S.A	FR	Company
Polymem S.A	FR	Company
HyGear B.V.	NL	Company
EcoRecycling SRL	IT	Company
ZEG Power A.S.	NO	Company
Quantis Sàrl	CH	Company
KT-Kinetics Technology SPA	IT	Company
Oficemen	ES	Network organization
PTECO2	ES	Network organization
CO ₂ Value Europe	BE	Network organization
MATERPLAT	ES	Network organization
Swedish Energy Agency	SE	Network organization
ANCRE	FR	Network organization
Association of Chemical Industry of the Czech Republic	CZ	Network organization
EMIRI	BE	Network organization
GDR Solar Fuels French Network	FR	Network organization
Innovation Quarter	NL	Network organization
DECHEMA	DE	Network organisation

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Fonden Teknologirådet	DK	Funding agency
Polish Ministry of Science and Education	PO	Ministry
Regional Ministry of E&R in comunidad de Madrid	ES	Municipality

Table 4: *Overview of selected European research organisations and companies interested to contribute to SUNRISE roadmap task group 4: Sustainable production of commodity chemicals and (jet) fuels*

Organization name	Country	Organization type
University of Torino	IT	University
Technical University of Munich	DE	University
Technical University of Delft	NL	University
Aachen University	DE	University
University of Leipzig	DE	University
Polytechnic University of Milano	IT	University
Technical University of Eindhoven	NL	University
University Paris Saclay	FR	University
University of Lille	FR	University
Aarhus University	DK	University
University of Oslo	NO	University
Ghent University	BE	University
University of Groningen	NL	University
Jagiellonian University_Dept. of Chemistry	PO	University
Dept. of Economics_Univ. Roma Tre	IT	University
University of Amsterdam	NL	University
University Grenoble Alpes	FR	University
Tel Aviv University	IL	University
Univ. of the West of England, Bristol	UK	University
University College London	UK	University
Queen's University Belfast	UK	University
Bogazici University	TR	University
Lund University	SE	University
National University of Ireland Galway (NUIG)	IRL	University
University of Twente	NL	University
National University of Ireland Galway	IR	University
Warsaw University of Life Sciences	PO	University
University of Milano-Bicocca	IT	University
Technical University Berlin	DE	University
Abo Akademi University	FI	University
European Atlas of Universities in Energy Research & Education, EUA-EPUE	BE	University network
Psi-K	CH	Academic network
UK Solar Fuels Network	UK	University network
Swedish Consortium for Artificial Photosynthesis	SE	University network
UK catalysis hub	UK	University network
UK Solar Fuels Network	UK	University network
Swedish Consortium for Artificial Photosynthesis	SE	University network
INSTM	IT	University network
European Materials Research Society, EMRS		Academic network
French Academy of Sciences	FR	Academic society
PTChem	PO	Academic society
Societa Chimica Italiana, SCI	IT	Academic society
Société Chimique de France	FR	Academic society
F.R.S.-FNRS	BE	Academic network
Polish National Science Centre (NCN)	PO	Academic network
University of Montpellier	FR	University
KU Leuven	BE	University
University of Lyon	FR	University
University of Helsinki	DK	University

Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne	CH	University
Cardiff University	UK	University
Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg	DE	University
Cambridge University	UK	University
Uppsala University	SE	University
Imperial College	UK	University
University of Copenhagen	DK	University
Italian National Research Council (CNR)	IT	Institute
ICIQ	ES	Institute
CIEMAT	ES	Institute
CNRS	FR	Institute
DLR	DE	Institute
TNO	NL	Institute
Flemish Institute for Technological Research VITO	BE	Institute
ENEA	IT	Institute
IFP Energies Nouvelles, IFPEN	FR	Institute
VTT Finland	FI	Institute
Bauhaus Luftfahrt	DE	Institute
ICFO Institut de Ciències Fotòniques	ES	Institute
Institute of Electronic Materials Technology (ITME)	PO	Institute
MPI für Kohlenforschung Mülheim	DE	Institute
Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH	DE	Institute
Karlsruhe Institute of Catalysis	DE	Institute
CEA	FR	Institute
Acconia	ES	Institute
CIC Energigune	ES	Institute
Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion	DE	Institute
Helmholtz centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Leipzig	DE	Institute
KTH	SE	Institute
ISPT	NL	Institute
DIFFER	NL	Institute
Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, ACIB	AT	Institute
D. G. de Investigación e Innovación Tecnológica	ES	Institute
IMEC	BE	Institute
3M	ES	Company
Acciona Energy	PT	Company
EDP Energia	ES	Company
ENAGAS	ES	Company
Repsol	ES	Company
Total S.A.	FR	Company
Toyota Motor Europe	BE	Company
Uniper	DE	Company
Covestro	DE	Company
Shell	NL	Company
Arcelor Mittal	LU	Company
Copenhagen airports	DK	Company
Avantium	NL	Company
Carbon Recycling International, CRI	IS	Company
Esy-labs	DE	Company

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Everest Coatings	NL	Company
Siemens	DE	Company
Johnson Matthey	UK	Company
Engie	FR	Company
Fortum	FI	Company
Hydron Energy	NL	Company
PEPPERPRINT	DE	Company
Photanol	NL	Company
PowerCell	SE	Company
Proheat – Heat Traces	ES	Company
PVH Energy Storage	ES	Company
SCM Amsterdam	NL	Company
Photanol	NL	Company
Casale	CH	Company
Neste	FI	Company
Stena Line	SE	Company
Clariant	CH	Company
Haldor Topsoe	DK	Company
RWE Power	DE	Company
Nextchem – Maire Tecnimont	IT	Company
Arcelor Mittal	LU	Company
Stamicarbon	NL	Company
Yara	NO	Company
C&CS catalysts and chemical specialties	DE	Company
Petrogal SA	PT	Company
Arkema France	FR	Company
Atmostat - Alcen	FR	Company
CEGASA	ES	Company
Certech	BE	Company
Ecoduna Eparella GmbH	AT	Company
Fev GmbH	DE	Company
GreenWin	BE	Company
Ingenza	UK	Company
Liquid Wind	SE	Company
Mügge GmbH	DE	Company
KT-Kinetics Technology SPA	IT	Company
ANCRE	FR	Network organization
Association of Chemical Industry of the Czech Republic	CZ	Network organization
GDR Solar Fuels French Network	FR	Network organization
Innovation Quarter	NL	Network organization
Swedish Energy Agency	SE	Network organization
MATERPLAT	ES	Network organization
DECHEMA	DE	Network organisation
EuChemS - European Chemical Society	BE	Society
Fonden Teknologirådet	DK	Funding agency
Deutsche Energie Agentur DENA	DE	Funding agency
Polish Economic chamber of Renewable and distributed energy (PIGEOR)	PO	Government body
Polish Ministry of Science and Education	PO	Ministry
Regional Ministry of E&R in comunidad de Madrid	ES	Municipality

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